

Deliverable 2.6 – WP2
Summary on current practices and methodologies of Thematic Networks (TNs)

EURAKNOS

*Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European
Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System*

TASK 2.5

Summary

Task description: WP2 aims to compile and evaluate EIP-AGRI outputs, in particular the outcomes of the Thematic Network (TNs). Task 2.5 Exchanging and compiling knowhow supports Tasks 2.1, 2.2; 2.3 and 2.4 that will evaluate the 28 TNs on content, design of their knowledge reservoirs, communication and dissemination strategies, and multi-actor approaches.

The aim of Deliverable 2.6 is, based on the analysis of the current practices and methodologies of 28 Thematic networks (TNs) (Task 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, and 2.4) to make a summary of best TN practices and methodologies and provide an impact assessment framework through the identification of indicators. The report gives an overview of the best practices based on D2.1 Report on content and structures data provision and knowledge formats of TNs, D2.2 Report on the format and designing of knowledge reservoirs of TNs, D2.3 Report on used communication and dissemination tools, and information channels, and D2.4 Report on multi-actor approach in the short, medium, and long term of TNs.

The indicators, qualitative as well as quantitative were grouped into the four main categories of the aspects that were studied in the previous Tasks: (i) content, (ii) storage of content, (iii) communication and dissemination (and exploitation), and (iv) multi-actor approach (MAA). In total 29 qualitative and 35 quantitative indicators were identified based on TN experiences. These constitute a framework for **future TNs to be inspired to formulate indicators that fits their specific network and objectives**. By providing these indicators for numerous purposes, future TN's will be guided **to achieve a larger impact in terms of uptake of results by the end-users, farmers, foresters, and advisors**.

The report provides input to WP3, which will validate these best practices and methodologies with end-users and formulate technical guidelines.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

4D4F – Data Driven Dairy Decisions for Farmers
ACTA – Association de Coordination Technique Agricole
AgriDemo-F2F – Building an interactive AgriDemo-Hub community: enhancing farmer to farmer learning (project)
AGRIFORVALOR – Adding value to biomass side streams
ARC – Agricultural Research Centre
AU – Aarhus University
AUA – Agricultural University of Athens
C&D – Communication and Dissemination
CDG – Civil Dialogue Group
CSA – Coordinated and Support Action
EIP – European Innovation Partnerships
EIP-AGRI – Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
EUFRUIT – The European Fruit Network
EURODAIRY – European network for dairy farming
EV ILVO – Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek
F2F – Farmer to Farmer
FAIR – Findable Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FarmDemo – Farm Demonstration (project)
FERTINNOWA – Transfer of INNOvative techniques for sustainable Water use in FERTigated crops
GLZ – Gruenlandzentrum Niedersachsen/Bremen EV
HENNOVATION – Animal welfare innovation
HIKR – High Impact Knowledge Reservoir
IDELE – Institut de l’Elevage
IfA – Innovation for Agriculture
Inno4Grass – Shared Innovation Space for Sustainable Productivity of Grasslands in Europe
KIP – Knowledge Innovation Partners
KPI – Key Performance Indicators
KR – Knowledge Reservoirs
LFG – Leap Forward Group
MA – Multi-Actor
MAA – Multi-Actor Approach
MAP – Multi-Actor Project
NAK – Magyar Agrar-, Élel miszergazdasági Es Vidékfejlesztési Kamara
NEFERTITI – Networking European Farms to Enhance Cross Fertilisation and Innovation Uptake through Demonstration (project)
NRN – National Rural Networks
NUTRIMAN – NUTRIent MANagement and Nutrient Recovery Thematic Network
OG – Operational Group
OK-Net Arable – Organic Knowledge Network Arable
OK-Net EcoFeed – Organic Knowledge Network on Monogastric Animal Feed
PA – Practice Abstracts
PLAID – Peer-to-Peer Learning: Accessing Innovation through Demonstration (project)
PSKW – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt Sint-Katelijne-Waver

RAU – Royal Agricultural University

SFT – Smart Farming Technology

SheepNet – Sharing Expertise and Experience towards sheep Productivity through NETworking

SMART-AKIS – European Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems towards innovation-driven research in Smart Farming Technology

SUWANU – Sustainable Water treatment and Nutrient reuse options

TN – Thematic Network

UGent – Ghent University

USC – Universidad de Santiago de Compostela

Winetwork – Network for the exchange and transfer of innovative knowledge between European wine-growing regions to increase the productivity and sustainability of the sector

WP – Work Package

1. Introduction

This deliverable consists of 7 chapters and an annex. In chapter 1, *Introduction*, the context is described followed by the purpose of D2.6. Chapter 2, *Task members*, gives an overview of partners involved. In chapter 3, *Methodology*, it is explained how knowledge collected in D2.1-4 is combined with recommendations from the Budapest workshops and how indicators for impact are drawn. In chapter 4, *Indicators*, indicators are defined and it is explained how and when to use indicators. Chapter 4 is the basis for understanding why work is done in chapter 5. Chapter 5, *Content and results*, consists of 4 main parts. Each part refers to four main sources from where indicators are extracted: 5.1: *Summary of current practices and methodologies in TNs*. Based on desktop studies, Face-to-face interviews, and surveys, Tasks 2.1-2.4 have identified practices conducted by 28 finalised and ongoing TNs. From these findings, the four tasks came up with recommendations for future TNs, these are referred to in this section. 5.2: *Twenty recommendations for future TNs combined with qualitative and quantitative impact indicators for TNs*. The results from the four tasks with different topics were presented for Knowledge Innovation Panel Members (KIPs) at the two days Budapest workshops. The KIPs were invited to discuss the practices identified in finalised and ongoing TNs. The KIPs contributed to the development of 20 recommendations for future TNs. The twenty recommendations are listed and for each recommendation, where possible, relevant text from D2.1-4 is combined with the recommendation, and useful indicators are extracted and listed in a table for each recommendation. All indicators are summed up in a complete table to conclude 5.2. In section 5.3, *Impact measured in nine thematic Network reports*, Reports from the already finalised TNs are examined to extract qualitative and quantitative indicators for output, outcome, and impact, and conclusions on indicators are drawn. To be sure that as many relevant indicators as possible were collected, an on-line brainstorm for all EURAKNOS partners was set up. The result of this brainstorm is referred to in section 5.4, *Indicators for impact extracted from the EURAKNOS mind map*. Chapter 6, *Discussion and Conclusion*, it is discussed how the indicators listed in chapter 5 can be used for evaluating the probability of impact. It is also explained how to select indicators. Chapters 7, the *Next step*, tells that D2.6 will feed into WP3 and further work in EURAKNOS. The annex, *Mind map of indicators*, shows the mindmap developed in collaboration with partners in EURAKNOS in an online tool.

1.1. Context

1.1.1. Project overview

EURAKNOS is a thematic network (TN) created to collate knowledge from all TNs to build a single community. At the beginning of the project, the state of play was that a set of 29 H2020 TNs, including EURAKNOS is collecting best practices and methodologies of 28 TNs. These TNs have the potential to maximise the uptake and impact of new knowledge by stimulating shared learning and coordinating the dissemination of practical information.

EURAKNOS aims to strengthen the EU agricultural knowledge base by co-creating ‘the network to connect all thematic networks’. To achieve this objective, EURAKNOS will:

- Facilitate and support thematic networks, link similar initiatives at EU and national levels and feed into national educational and training programmes;
- Widen and connect existing thematic networks to build knowledge reservoirs within the agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI);

- Collect, evaluate and compare knowledge, materials, and tools that have been produced by thematic networks and operational groups;
- Develop a harmonised approach by producing technical guidelines on how to make a high-impact knowledge reservoir;
- Develop a blueprint for creating an EU-wide, dynamic, open-source agricultural knowledge innovation database, and explore the value of doing this.

1.1.2. Work Package 2

Work Package (WP) 2 aims to make an evaluation of past and running thematic networks (28) (crops, livestock, forestry, and horizontal themes such as water and fertilization) and other EIP-AGRI highly related activities. In particular, WP2 will:

- Analyse the type of data and the ways data are produced, collected and stored in the current H2020 TNs;
- Evaluate the format and design of Knowledge Reservoirs (KR) (as open sources) within current and past TNs, related H2020 Multi Actor (MA) projects and linked Operational Groups (OG)
- Assess dissemination and communication activities, materials and tools on their respective impact towards the end-users, farmers, foresters and advisors, used by TNs;
- Analyse the multi-actor approach (MAA) used by TNs on the short, medium and long term;
- Exchange and compile the experiences and know-how of the TNs with a focus on the end-user groups: farmers, foresters, and advisors.

1.2. Objectives - Purpose of deliverable D2.6

The deliverables of WP2 (D2.1 Report on content and structures of data provision of TNs, D2.2 Report on format and design of knowledge reservoirs of TNs, D2.3, Report on used communication and dissemination tools, information channels of TNs, and D2.4 Report on the multi-actor approach in the short term, medium and long term of TNs) are mainly the reports of the four activities carried out in Tasks 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, and 2.4 to prepare the first EURAKNOS workshop (Budapest 11-13 September 2019). These activities have summarised the efforts done in the 28 TNs on (i) data provision, (ii) content and knowledge formats, format and design of knowledge reservoirs, (iii) communication and dissemination tools, and (iv) multi-actor approaches. Based on this, D2.5, Report of EURAKNOS workshop 1, sums up 20 recommendations for an ideal TN, distilled from the workshop in Budapest.

This deliverable, D2.6, draws the main conclusions from D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, and D2.4 on current practices and methodologies of TNs and combines these with the twenty recommendations derived from the first EURAKNOS workshop in Budapest, summarised in D2.5. This is used as a basis to come up with quantitative and qualitative indicators as a basis to enhance the efficiency and hence the impact of TNs. The list of indicators was enriched with nine final TN reports on the achieved impact and with a mind map exercise by the EURAKNOS consortium (including TN coordinators and partners). The results will feed into WP3 that will define the design of a High Knowledge Impact Reservoir (HIKR) and formulate technical guidelines.

2. Task members

Below you can find an example of a table with task members.

Table 1. Partners involved in the different Tasks of WP 2 (bold represents the task leaders).

Task	Partner													
	ACTA	IDELE	NAK	UGent	GLZ	USC	AU	PSKW	ARC	AUA	IFA	LFG	RAU	EV ILVO
2.1	X	X	X	X	X	X		X						
2.2	X	X	X	X		X	X			X				
2.3	X	X	X	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	
2.4	X	X	X	X	X		X		X					
2.5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

3. Methodology

Based on desktop studies, face-to-face interviews, and surveys, Tasks 2.1-2.4 have identified practices conducted by 28 finalised and ongoing TNs. From these findings, the four tasks came up with recommendations for future TNs referred to in section 5.1. Results from the four tasks with different topics were presented for Knowledge Innovation Panel Members (KIPs) at the Budapest workshops. The KIPs were invited to discuss the practices identified in finalised and ongoing TNs. The KIPs contributed to the development of 20 recommendations for future TNs.

The summary of the TN current practices and methodologies as identified in Tasks 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, and 2.4 and described in D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, and D2.4 is presented in this deliverable. Based on this summary, the Budapest recommendations, and reports from the already finalised TNs have been examined to extract qualitative and quantitative indicators for output, outcome, and impact. Conclusions on indicators are drawn in section 5.3.

Besides relevant indicators were identified in an on-line brainstorm, using the Mindmeistertool¹, for all EURAKNOS partners. The result of this brainstorm is referred to in section 5.4.

The summary and the impact indicators will be used as a basis for WP3 that will select the best practices and methodologies for TNs for creating content, designing the knowledge reservoirs, communication and dissemination, and multi-actor approaches. They will also be used to develop technical guidelines for TNs to be more effective in reaching the farmers, foresters, and advisors, and speed up the uptake of the outputs. The indicators can also be used by the TNs as criteria for a framework to achieve a better impact.

¹ <https://www.mindmeister.com/>

4. Indicators

4.1. Need for indicators linked to the impact

In Horizon 2020 – indicators it says that “[i]n the context of tighter budgets and more public attention to the effectiveness of public funding and EU-funded research, there is a need to demonstrate the performance, impact and added value of EU programmes. [...] Horizon 2020 marks a shift towards the use of indicators that aim to capture results and impacts”.

“Assessing impact require reliable indicators”, however, “reliable indicators of results and impacts are limited, the importance of individual indicators varies by discipline and sector, and there can be a considerable time lag between inputs and outputs” ([Horizon2020 indicators](#)).

Before choosing indicators for impact, it is important to understand what is possible to measure, how, and when.

H2020 TNs have two main aims:

- **Collecting** existing scientific knowledge and best practices, which are close to being put into practice but not yet sufficiently ready for farmers and foresters to implement.
- **Sharing and presenting: translating** this knowledge into easily understandable end-user material such as short informative recommendations and solutions (“practice abstracts”), leaflets, guidelines, and audio-visual material (photos, video clips, etc.) to be able to share and present it. This material should be made available **beyond the lifespan of the project** through the main existing dissemination channels that farmers often use, as well as through the EIP-AGRI website: www.eip-agri.eu ([Thematic network under Horizon2020](#)).

EURAKNOS aims to provide qualitative and quantitative indicators for impacts concerning:

TN content – creation of outputs,

TN content storage – how outputs are stored,

TN Communication & Dissemination – uptake and promotion of outputs and

TN multi-actor approach – who to involve and how.

TNs point of origin is the existing scientific knowledge. The *intervention* of a TN goes from *inputs* over *activities* to *outputs* and may end up with *outcomes (results)*. However, the TN is only in control of *inputs, activities, and outputs*. By successful completion, the TN can obtain *influence* through inputs, activities, outputs, and outcomes (*results*). The impact is in the highest *interest* of the TN but is beyond its control and influence.

Example: Inputs and certain *activities* will be put into action during the lifespan of the TN and then *outputs* in the form of e.g. practice abstracts, videos, or many other things will be developed. If users of the *output* obtain new knowledge and e.g. adopt new habits of feeding animals, the TN has also provided *outcomes*, sometimes named *results*. If this change of behaviour persists beyond the lifespan of the TN and even spread to more farmers and several countries, the TN has provided *impact*. That is the uppermost aim of a TN.

Therefore indicators are needed to ensure that a TN does the best possible on its way from inputs over activities to outputs and hopefully results - outcomes.

The report D2.6 suggests indicators for impacts obtained in TNs divided into four different categories: TN content, TN content storage, TN Communication & Dissemination, TN multi-actor approach.

4.2. Definition of output, outcome (results), impact and indicators

Definitions from Horizon2020 indicators:

- *Outputs* are what is directly produced or supplied through the EU intervention. They often relate to the expected deliverables of the intervention. Outputs generally occur within the short to medium term.
- *Outcome (Results)* capture more direct, short to medium term changes in a situation.
- *Impact* broadly defines the wider societal, economic, or environmental cumulative changes over a longer period.
- *Indicators* are defined as the measurement of an objective to be met, a resource mobilised, an effect obtained, or a context variable.
- *Output indicators* relate to the specific deliverables of the intervention.
- *Outcome (Result) indicators* represent the immediate effects of the measure concerned and look at its direct addressees.
- *Impact indicators* represent what the successful outcome should be in terms of impact on the economy/society beyond those directly affected by the intervention

4.3. Qualitative and quantitative indicators in D2.6

Qualitative and quantitative criteria are developed based on:

1. 28 finalised and ongoing TNs (D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)
2. the workshop in Budapest with 32 KIPs participating (D2.5)
3. nine final TN reports
4. a mind map developed in collaboration with partners in EURAKNOS

In the following chapters, the summary of current practices and methodologies of TNs is presented, followed by qualitative and quantitative indicators for TNs to achieve a better impact. In the context of this report, they will be referred to as indicators or output indicators as they present proxy indicators and not real impact indicators for measuring the uptake of TN results or outputs in the field. Moreover, the list of indicators presented here may have limitations. They are not exhaustive for the performance of TNs as they related to four key aspects and are presented based on four sources.

This report may however serve as a basis to further develop criteria to achieve a better impact with TNs. Indicators presented here can be used for the development of the Technical Guidelines and as a source of inspiration for TNs to increase their efficiency and hence impact.

5. Content and results

5.1. Summary of current practices and methodologies of Thematic Networks

For the work of Tasks 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, and 2.4, the information that was published on the websites of the TNs was used as material to develop the initial EURAKNOS desktop study on content collected by TNs. The desk study was completed by a questionnaire and surveys that were carried out within 28 TNs (for a detailed overview of the methodology, see D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, and D2.4). Also, the workshop held in Budapest in September 2019 helped to finalize the evaluation and validate the outputs of the aforementioned Tasks.

5.1.1. Summary of D2.1 'Report on content and structures of data provision and knowledge formats of Thematic Networks'

The global data analysis showed that the majority of TNs were dealing with arable crops, livestock, and agroforestry or forestry. These were mainly allocated to urban and lowland areas and targeted cooperatives, family- and collective farming. TNs were working with large and small farms, respectively, which was mostly traditional but also transitional farming systems. Primarily, the data gathered by the TNs had research and farming origin as this is the aim of this type of Coordinated and Support Action (CSA) project. Regarding content, TNs were by far linked to fertilization and water management, while the Practice Abstracts (PAs) and Operational groups (OGs) were mostly related to farming systems and specific crops. Overall, the TNs produced 24 types of dissemination/communication materials (range 2-14). The most popular types of materials were the PAs and the factsheets. The least popular material was podcasts and videos. However, most of the effort recognized by the TNs was related to the videos besides the PA and factsheets. Finally, TNs contributed to the inclusion of higher farm outputs while those projects related to the National Rural Networks (NRNs) produced more infographics as an easy form to reach policymakers. Projects with a higher number of linkages to other TNs, OGs, and NRNs, had a higher number of outputs related to practices, while those with a higher number of OG connections used more data from advisors.

5.1.2. Summary of D2.2 'Report on format and design of knowledge reservoirs of Thematic Networks'

The large diversity of approaches within the various TNs was reflected in contents and KRs. TNs have different websites with different IT structures, formats, and contents, which was due to, among others, the various actors involved in the project, the theme, the sector, the targeted audience as well as the country and the output of the project. To reach a high level of impact, results must be of high relevance to the end-user in addition to being easily accessible and understandable. Sustainability of the website is a key issue in terms of long-term impact. Thus, a generic website or platform may be created with short descriptions and links to the individual project websites built in a common format. When designing a KR, it is essential to take into account the need and expectations of the end-users. This entails knowing what type of content end-users expect in addition to defining the functionalities offered by the KR. Also, it would be of relevance to plan the development of a prototype that can be presented to a panel of end-

users, with different profiles, who will then be able to give their opinions and share their perceptions. Indicators such as the number of hits for specific information or profile of the end-user can be used for continuous monitoring, evaluation, and adaptation of the system.

5.1.3. Summary of D2.3 ‘Report on used communication and dissemination tools, and information channels of Thematic Networks’

The impact of Communication and Dissemination (C&D) was not as successful as expected and appeared to be a constraint for TN partners. Languages and translations remained the main barrier. The distinction between C&D is not that simple and clear. Measuring engagement and uptake of end-users in C&D activities is highly complicated, as well as the success of the channels, tools, and materials. Currently, there is no effective tool to measure impact. Hence, it is advisable to recruit professional communication and dissemination partners. Usually, target audiences were properly identified in the C&D plans. The most successful channel of communication was the project website. However, the dissemination materials with technical content and best practices were not easily accessible on the platforms. Social networks were promising communication channels but also time-consuming. It was more difficult to reach the targeted end-users through European projects compared to domestic and local projects. The best way to reach a farmer was through peers. Most TNs expressed a lack of time to efficiently disseminate results during the project lifetime as a substantial part of the results emerge in the very last months of the project. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were rarely mentioned in C&D Plans and linked to the C&D channels of the projects. The main objective of TNs was to disseminate to end-users and present ready to use techniques and best practices in agriculture. However, there was a lack of ‘impact culture’ within the Research and Innovation community composing most of the TNs. Also, there was a lack of concern and tools to monitor the outreach of the TNs through qualitative analysis.

5.1.4. Summary of D2.4 ‘Report on multi-actor approach in the short, medium and long-term of Thematic Networks’

The main type of actors engaged in TN’s were academic institutions and research organizations, followed by enterprises, associations, advisory centres, and applied research institutions with an advisory role, primary producers, and governmental institutions. Media, non-governmental institutions (NGO’s), consumers, and dedicated educational institutions were underrepresented. These groups of actors were equally important in the AKIS and must be more involved in TNs in the frame of MAA. In particular, innovation brokers and educational institutions (e.g. vocational schools and advisory training) play a major intermediary role in the uptake of results and must be much more involved in consortia and through participatory activities. Eastern European countries should be more involved in TNs to bridge the division between Eastern and Western Europe. Only half of the TNs were 100% demand-driven, thus, not oriented towards the end-users’ needs. Furthermore, there is a need to involve more early adopters. Linking to OGs and local end-user groups is useful. Farmers must be approached in an informal setting and in an environment that creates trust. No size fits all. Therefore, a range of strategies must be applied, which take form during the conceptualization phase, preferably with the involvement of all actors, in particular end-user groups, advisors, farmers, and foresters. The MAA is considered a key to contribute to the content creation of the KR produced by the TNs and also to content for advisory systems and

networking. The facilitator model to involve local end-user groups was successfully deployed in several TNs such as Hennovation², Sheepnet³, and Winetwork⁴. To be fully efficient, the MAA of TNs must be linked to the European, national, regional, and local levels. This can be achieved by the involvement of e.g. European umbrella organizations, NRN, and local networks. A post-project phase is needed to evaluate the outcome and uptake of results by end-users. Further reflections are needed in terms of how to do this, including which type of evaluation methodologies and indicators are needed.

5.2. Twenty recommendations for Thematic Networks combined with qualitative and quantitative impact indicators for Thematic Networks

The twenty recommendations for an ideal TN distilled from the various parallel workshops that were organized during the EURAKNOS Thematic Network expert meeting in Budapest, September 2019 (D2.5) are grouped into categories of:

- **TN content** – creation of outputs
- **TN content storage** – how outputs are stored
- **TN Communication & Dissemination** – uptake and promotion of outputs
- **TN multi-actor approach** who to involve and how.

From these recommendations and the D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4 on content, content storage, communication & dissemination, and the multi-actor approach respectively, qualitative and quantitative indicators are extracted as criteria for TNs to be more efficient in reaching end users, farmers, foresters, and advisors, and hence create more impact in terms of uptake of results. These indicators are as such not measuring the uptake of the results but only indicators for better TN practices and methodologies as to create more impact, and are therefore referred to as output indicators or indicators. The key to distilling these indicators from the WP2 evaluation and Budapest recommendations was as such based on TN experiences on how to be better orient TNs to end-users in all aspects, content, content storage, communication & dissemination, and the multi-actor approach. The related text from D2.1-2.4 is added below each recommendation and the indicators extracted from the text are listed in a table below the recommendation they belong to. All indicators are presented in a table at the end of the chapter to increase the overview.

5.2.1. Major conclusions and impact indicators related to the content of knowledge collected and shared by Thematic Networks

TN content (creation of outputs)

Task 2.1 relates to the type of data and the ways data are produced, collected, and stored in TNs. More specifically, this relates to the content and type of knowledge that is collected in TNs and the format in which the knowledge has been stored.

² <http://www.hennovation.eu/>

³ <http://www.sheepnet.network/>

⁴ <http://www.winetwork.eu/>

Below are the recommendations for an ideal TN, distilled from the workshop in Budapest with combined with findings from Task 2.1 (D.2.1 Report on content and structures of data provision and knowledge formats of TNs) related to the content of knowledge collected and shared by TNs. Based on these selected recommendations and solutions, quantitative and qualitative indicators have been formulated.

Budapest recommendation 1: TN Purpose

Regarding: **TN content**, **TN multi-actor approach**, TN Communication & Dissemination

The TN should have a **clear and narrow focus** on the problem it wants to solve within a certain sector **by** asking end-users the right questions to **understand and address the needs, problems, preferences & barriers of end-users**.

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D2.1:

‘Most of the TNs deal with agricultural lands such as crops (permanent crops and arable crops) and livestock. Regarding the land use of the existing TNs associated with the CAP sectors, it was appreciated that most of the TN data outputs are linked to agricultural, with over 4000 records produced compared with the low production of agroforestry and forestry. Moreover, TNs are quite focussed on these categories, as 63,6% of the TNs are dealing with just one topic but almost 40% with two or more.

TNs are mainly tackling cooperatives, but also family and collective farms. Cooperative and collective farming are forms of optimizing the use of the resources and better organizing the sales. However, few TNs are exclusively linked to one of these types of farming, being 67% of the TNs targeting the three types of aforementioned farm organizations.

TNs deal with full and part-time farmers, mostly women working in cooperatives, although not exclusively, being both large and small traditional farms in conventional and organic farming.’

Table 2. Collected and shared knowledge – TN purpose

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Content	Qualitative	Quantitative	
Purpose	Problem-solving approach		Needs of farmers, foresters and advisors
	A well-defined, clear scope		Goals defined during the conceptualisation phase

Budapest recommendation 2: TN State Of The Art

Regarding: **TN content**

The TN should also have or gather an **extensive overview** of the content that **already exists (relevant state of the art) about the subject it wants to deal with. The TN should know how it will utilise the existing** coordination and support measures to apply, add value, and go beyond the existing body of knowledge. This phase enables the TN to decide whether there are enough knowledge and expertise within the TN, or whether there is a need to do more preparatory work or engage other experts.

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D2.1:

‘All TNs are dealing with rural areas but some of them also with periurban (32%) and urban (23%) areas, which means that they are connecting rural, periurban and urban lands that can be linked to the bioeconomy framework’.

‘Around 26% of the TNs are exclusively associated with lowlands, usually the most productive lands and only 5% of the TNs work in mountain areas, which may limit innovation in these areas, where it is strongly needed from an environment point of view’.

‘The origin of the data produced in the TNs comes from researchers (22 out of 24), farmers/foresters (21 out of 24), and advisors (18 out of 24). There are also 13 TNs that use other sources of information such as industries or facilitators. TNs offering innovative solutions are those not choosing farmers or foresters as a source of information’.

‘The number of partners involved in TNs is also higher in Western Europe than in Eastern Europe. By sectors, arable crops are not represented by TNs accordingly to the area arable land covers, leaving many eastern and southern regions not tackled due to lower extension services development’.

Table 3. Collected and shared knowledge - TN State of the Art

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Content	Qualitative	Quantitative	
Knowledge	State of the art knowledge collected early in the period of a TN and shared with all TN partners		State of the art review of existing knowledge research and grey literature
		No. of disciplines involved in the TN consortium in the conceptualization phase	Shared competences of all TN-partners
		No. of disciplines involved in the TN activities during the project.	An updated list of topics, activities, and participants during the lifespan of a TN
Knowledge and regions		Equal distribution in the consortium between partners in different European regions	No. of partners in consortium per European region

 Budapest recommendation 7: TN Content

Regarding: [TN content](#)

The **outputs** that the TN produces should be **based on the practical expertise** that can motivate farmers to apply or further innovate to tackle technological, financial, and ecological problems. The solutions should have clear targets and user profiles (+ expertise level) for the problems they

are trying to solve and they should be **embedded in everyday farming practices**. The role of a TN is (I) to create and share timely practical solutions by leveraging existing knowledge concerning technological, financial and ecological problems; and (II) to inspire other end-users and actors to mobilise new TNs or other MAPs to trial, innovate and apply their practical solutions to context-specific problems.

Table 4. Collected and shared knowledge - TN Content

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Content	Qualitative	Quantitative	
Purpose	Output relevant and practically applicable for users		Users' need for practical solutions

Budapest recommendation 8: TN Digital Platform

Regarding: **TN content**, **TN content storage**, TN Communication & Dissemination, **TN multi-actor approach**

The **digital platform** that houses the TNs knowledge outputs should be organised using common easy language with well-defined concepts and focus (instead of using over-generalised buzzwords).

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.1:

'The materials produced by TNs in a higher number are Practice Abstracts, Factsheets, Press Releases, Research articles (scientific papers), Reviews and Technical Articles, being 7.8 the median number of the materials produced and ranging from 2 to 14. So, most of the materials produced are text and video type, in a much higher proportion than image, presentation, excel files, and audio types. The lowest number of materials are produced as podcasts and others (e.g. leaflets, posters, on-line courses, and datasheets).'

'The language chosen to produce text and video materials is English in most of the cases, followed by German, Spanish, and French in a very low number. Nevertheless, the countries producing these materials in a higher number vary among the project members.

The highest effort on producing these materials is on Guides (Best practices guides), Practice Abstracts, Videos, Factsheets, Reports, and Reviews'.

Table 5. Collected and shared knowledge - TN Digital Platform

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Content	Qualitative	Quantitative	
Output	Easily understandable language		Knowledge of which languages users understand

	Terminology oriented to practitioners		Knowledge of common terminology among users
		No. of local languages per output	List of output and languages
		No. of different outputs	List of outputs

5.2.2. Major conclusions and impact indicators related to the design of knowledge reservoirs and shared by TNs

TN content storage (how outputs are stored)

Task 2.2 relates to the design of (open source) knowledge reservoirs (KRs) of TNs, more specifically it relates to the website of a TN and data platforms or knowledge clouds within a TN.

Below are the recommendations for an ideal TN, distilled from the workshop in Budapest with major conclusions of D.2.1 and task 2.2 (D2.2 Report on format and design of knowledge reservoirs of TNs) and task 2.3 (D2.3 Report on used communication and dissemination tools, and information channels of TNs) related to the content of knowledge collected and shared by TNs.

Based on these selected recommendations and solutions, quantitative and qualitative indicators have been formulated.

Budapest recommendation 8: TN Digital Platform

Regarding: **TN content**. **TN content storage**, TN Communication & Dissemination, **TN multi-actor approach**

The **digital platform** that houses the TNs knowledge outputs should function so the content shown to each user is **profile user-led i.e. tailored to their profile, level of expertise, and in their preferred language and format** (automatic profiling and translation). Having a digital platform, which corresponds to each user, creates trust and validity in the platform, which can amplify the number of users it reaches and the impact it gains.

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.2:

‘Most of the projects that dedicated a specific site to the KR function built it with some specific tools: Drupal, TYPO3 or Joomla have to be used for instance. Those languages provided an opportunity to organise the content to answer to user demand. Those have been used because of their functionalities such as the ability to add members to the community’.

‘It should be noted that of the 12 open-source KRs that have specific search engine tools, only 1 (SUWANU⁵) is a KR previously qualified as ‘integrated into project site’. The other 11 are either KRs “hosted

⁵ <https://suwanu-europe.eu/>

on a dedicated platform" (EUFRUIT⁶, Inno4Grass⁷, OK-Net Arable⁸, OK-Net EcoFeed⁹, SMART-AKIS¹⁰, WINETWORK¹¹) or KRs in their own right hosted by project site (AFINET¹², NUTRIMAN¹³ and SheepNet¹⁴).

Table 6. Design of knowledge reservoirs - TN Digital Platform

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Content storage	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	User-friendly access		User tests
	Search engine tool		Knowledge of users' needs
	Automatic profiling and translation		Knowledge of users' profile and language
		No. of user-friendly functionalities	User tests

Budapest recommendation 9: TN User Interaction

Belongs to: **TN content**, **TN content storage**, TN Communication & Dissemination, **TN multi-actor approach**

Besides, the digital platform should **include user analytics** to further optimize usability, including **evaluation and feedback forms** on the solutions and outputs generated. For example, via user reviews of content, content suggestions (e.g. Amazon function: 'user that were interested in this were also interested in these alternatives') or a 'bot' that flags up other information that is relevant for you in an interactive virtual conversation (Q&A). This would facilitate a live, interactive experience for the user and enable the TN **to improve the outputs and adapt them**, so they stay relevant (see the iterative spiral from the 'Community of Practice'). E.g. 4D4F¹⁵, *measured outreach with user analytics in a learning community e.g. FarmDemo hub that was set*

⁶ <http://eufirin.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.inno4grass.eu/en/>

⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/ok-net-arable-%E2%80%93-organic-knowledge-network-arable>

⁹ <https://ok-net-ecofeed.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.smart-akis.com/>

¹¹ <http://www.winetwork.eu/>

¹² <https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/afinet>

¹³ <https://nutriman.net/>

¹⁴ <http://www.sheepnet.network/>

¹⁵ <https://4d4f.eu/>

up by AgriDemo-F2F¹⁶, PLAID¹⁷, and NEFERTITI¹⁸ uses questions, instead of keywords or categories to guide the users to the results that are most relevant for them.

Table 7. Design of knowledge reservoirs – TN User Interaction

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Content storage	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	Digital platform with possibilities for user analytics		Definitions of useful analytic techniques. Content rating tools.
	User interactive digital platform		Knowledge of applicable techniques and layout
		No. of interactions on digital platform	Counts of interactions. Traffic analytics

Budapest recommendation 14: TN Digital Support

Regarding: **TN content storage**, TN Communication & Dissemination, **TN multi-actor approach**

The TN should provide **digital support structures** that allow **sharing problems, expertise, solutions and that can bring actors together**. This should be done **engagingly and interactively**, e.g. via a chat forum, WebTV with videos or podcasts to engage young potential farmers, and allow farmers to ask each other for help and facilitate questions and sharing of knowledge between users. Potentially, this could be built or interact with existing social media platforms, like Facebook, Instagram, or Reddit (e.g. Olivipedia).

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.2:

‘Language and layout attract less attention with regard to validation (below 78% of the KR). As far as involvement in different types of data validation is concerned, half of the KRs have applied more than 5 different validation types with applied validation types ranging from 3 to 5’.

‘TNs consider that all knowledge content is findable, whereas 89% is interoperable, 83% reusable and 71% accessible. Almost all TNs fulfill some of these characteristics, with a range from 1 to 4’.

‘One specific partner within a TN is generally responsible for the management and the design. But in several cases (with a frequency of 76%), the project coordinator and a Work Package (WP) leader are also involved with a high degree of co-responsibility’.

‘The IT language choice must also be compatible with the open-access character. Open access means that research results are made freely accessible in digital form, which promotes the dissemination of research

¹⁶ <https://agridemo-h2020.eu/the-project/>

¹⁷ <https://plaid-h2020.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://nefertiti-h2020.eu/>

results both within the scientific community and to the public at large. The reader can read free of charge, use, copy, print, and link to the open-access publications’.

‘Most commonly used feedback tool is traffic analytics because it works on any website. Among the other tools mentioned, it is noted that 17% of TNs use end-user surveys. The goal is to understand what end-users are looking for in terms of content. Some other TNs use social media tools. It is a way to promote some content and evaluate its popularity. Finally, few TNs have set up specific tools for content rating’.

‘To date, very few TNs have opted to host their content on open-access databases. The KRs we were able to identify, which has opted to host all the content available in its KR on the Zenodo open-access database are AFINET and Organic Farmknowledge (OK-Net Arable and OK-Net Ecofeed) through Organic Eprints’.

Table 8. Design of knowledge reservoirs - TN Digital Support

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Content storage	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	Involvement of a professional web designer		Competences for web design
	Attractive layout of the TN website		User tests
	Technical content and best practices easy to find on the website		User tests
	Open access according to the FAIR principle (FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE, REUSABLE)		Well defined specifications for the platform
	Interactive platform		Knowledge of applicable techniques and layout
	Evaluation and feedback mechanisms (surveys for rating by users)		
		User analytic numbers	Counting techniques
		Number of linkages on the website with social media	Counting techniques

Budapest recommendation 20: TN Sustainability

Regarding: [TN content storage](#)

The TN should be sustainable and ensure that the **project results stay available** for the intended target audiences and beyond, even after the project has ended. Besides, it must allow actors within the network to stay connected. This could be facilitated by an online digital platform or the continuation of meetings organised by the network themselves where they rotate the role of

the facilitator. Therefore, TNs need to address this point (the sustainability of the network) including matters related to governance and financing already during the lifetime of the TN.

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.2 and D2.3:

D2.2: ‘The majority 70% of TNs make the KR produced available as open-source on the project website. Only one-third of the TNs have a dedicated knowledge platform to host the KR. The majority of TNs (70%) provide access to their KRs through the TN’s website, whereas the KRs of one-third of the TNs are made available as a separate service’.

‘Some TNs choose to reference their KR on OpenAire, the scientific platform to exchange knowledge on agriculture. This solution gives some opportunities in storage data and information’.

‘44% Of the TN has an exploitation plan’.

‘It should be noted that the attendance rate of the KR is strongly correlated with the frequency with which content is updated. To retain the loyalty of a KR user, it is necessary to regularly provide the KR with new content adapted to the expectations of this user’.

*D.2.3: ‘In continuation, and to assure the sustainability and long-term application of TNs’ results, **links with long term local initiatives and education programs** are recommended’.*

*‘The difficulty to find time and budget for C&D raises the question **to manage independently these activities** (as well for demonstration and networking) **by other programs or complementary funding**. This can assure that C&D will be implemented by experts and that partners keep time to focus on the knowledge results’.*

Table 9. Design of knowledge reservoirs - TN Sustainability

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Content storage	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	An exploitation plan for the open-source knowledge reservoir of the TN.		Exploitation plan defined along with designing the reservoir
	Sustainability of the project’s website after the lifespan of the project		More budget and plan than data
		Number of linkages to networks	Counting possibilities on platform
		Number of linkages to external data repositories	Counting possibilities on platform
		Number of months that the website with TN outputs stays available	Not possible to measure within the lifespan of TN

		after the ending of the project	
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5.2.3. Major conclusions and impact indicators related to dissemination, communication, and information strategies collected and shared by TNs

TN Communication & Dissemination

Task 2.3 relates to the best ways to disseminate and communicate according to their impacts on the end-user groups, including materials, tools, and channels.

Below are listed the recommendations for an ideal TN, distilled from the workshop in Budapest with major findings of Task 2.1 (D.2.1 Report on content and structures of data provision and knowledge formats of TNs) and task 2.3 (D2.3 Report on used communication and dissemination tools, and information channels of TNs) related to the content of knowledge collected and shared by TNs.

Based on these selected recommendations and solutions, quantitative and qualitative indicators have been formulated.

Budapest recommendation 8: TN Digital Platform

Regarding: [TN content](#), [TN content storage](#), [TN Communication & Dissemination](#), [TN multi-actor approach](#)

The **digital platform** that houses the knowledge outputs of TNs should function so the content shown to each user is **profile user-led i.e. tailored to the profile in question, the level of expertise, and in the preferred language and format** (automatic profiling and translation).

Table 10. Communication and Dissemination - TN Digital Platform

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
C&D	Qualitative	Quantitative	
Materials		No. of scope related material	Clear scope List of material
		No. of problem-solving material	Users' needs List of material

Budapest recommendation 13: TN Assets Leveraging

Regarding: [TN Communication & Dissemination](#)

Local and well established existing networks (e.g. National Rural Networks (NRNs) or OGs), **channels** (e.g. media contacts, news outlets, or farmer organisations), **meetings, and activities should be used** as much as possible for getting relevant input and organising end-user communication and dissemination activities. Farmers & foresters only interact and take up information from materials, channels, and people they trust. This also includes other farmers they respect in their community. Therefore, a **mapping exercise to identify the resources farmers are**

using and their existing connections and support mechanisms for TNs is vital to ensure uptake of new information within the TN and wider dissemination throughout the farming community.

Table 11. Communication and Dissemination - TN Assets Leveraging

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
C&D	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	List of resources trusted by users		Mapping exercise on trusted channels
	Use of well-established networks and meeting		Mapping exercise on trusted networks and meetings

 Budapest recommendation 15: TN Training:

Regarding: **TN Communication & Dissemination**

Nonetheless, the TN should also target ‘analogue users’ and increase the digital literacy of their ‘end-users’ via **training/support**. The use of **professional teachers or links to a known and trusted education or training platform** can be an added value. It may also be effective to introduce ‘analogue users’ to digital platforms via traditional forms of knowledge exchange, such as discussion groups or F2F dissemination meetings. Here, the value and benefits of digital platforms can be established, as a means of bringing this community back together online.

Table 12. Communication and Dissemination - TN Training

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
C&D	Qualitative	Quantitative	
Training modules and webinars	Focused and involving teaching	No. of trainings	Participant surveys Count modules
		No. of webinars	Count webinars
	Training and education linked to existing education	No. of linkages with local training initiatives and educational programs for users	Mapping of existing education Count linkages
	Skilled teachers		Engaged teachers along with developing training Participant surveys

 Budapest recommendation 16: TN Peer-To-Peer Exchange

Regarding: **TN Communication & Dissemination**

The TN should take into account the **innovation adaptation curve** (innovator > early adopter > majority > laggards) and spend the majority of their focus on those ‘end-users’ they can reach

that act as **influencers** (80/20-rule). As such, it should have a clear strategy with support tools to leverage this knowledge transfer effect and allow farmers to communicate more with other farmers and exchange ideas via **F2F meetings and cross-visits**. Elements of gamification or organizing an award can also be useful. *E.g. Newbie award for new entrant business models as inspiration for other farmers.*

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.3:

‘According to TNs’ experiences, the most successful channel of communication is the website, and for dissemination, it is face to face meetings with end-users, especially farmers and foresters. Both activities should be organised in a complementary way with 1) social networks posts, newsletters and videos produced for communication, and 2) physical meetings as seminars, workshops, and field demonstration for dissemination.’

‘Social networks are promising communication channels but time-consuming ones. Partners are not using them enough, slowing down the development of the digital community. TN partners and other actors should be stimulated more to use social media and to spread messages about TN results to their peers’.

‘The identification of the audience may not be restricted to the type of actors, but also to their common practices, age, and preference in term of the channel – for example, a young farmer belonging to a digital community (twitter group, etc.) in comparison to an old farmer who doesn’t have any computer or smartphone, but is proactive in farmer associations’.

*‘Some channels are not used (or practically not) by TNs even if they are potential good relays of C&D to reach farmers/foresters, such as **WhatsApp, radio media, podcasts, and local press**’.*

*‘There is a need for **decision-making support tools** on how to select a blend of multiple channels and a portfolio or tools/materials that will lead to high impact communication to the specific audiences (including end-users of project results)’.*

*‘The communication strategy can be highly effective if you **visit each farmer in the country**, however, this strategy would be highly unaffordable as the people writing the projects are not communication specialists, nor enough support tools, etc. is provided to TNs to get this right’.*

Table 13 Communication and Dissemination - TN Peer-to-Peer Exchange

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
C&D	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	C&D format, tools, and channels according to the type of content and target audience		Mapping users preferred format, tools, and channels
	Subgroups of target audiences (younger versus older, male versus female etc.)		Knowing the diversity of users
		No. of specific channels used (podcast, radio, local agricultural, field days, studies, demo’s, peer	Count channels

		to peer) to reach a specific end-user audience	
	Professional C&D in the TN consortium or activities		Apply for competences in the conceptual phase
	Professional innovation brokers in the TN consortium or activities		Apply for competences in the conceptual phase

 Budapest recommendation 17: TN Output Format:

Regarding: **TN Communication & Dissemination**

In terms of the format, materials, and tools used for dissemination purposes, **the less text and more visual and interactive the better**. Hence, there should be a focus on creating **engaging videos of best practices or case examples** with co-created content and international showcases of new information.

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.3:

‘Even if the website is useful and appreciated by TNs, it seems that all dissemination materials with technical content and best practices are not easily accessible on the platforms. The mix of project presentations and results doesn’t allow us to have a simple and clear message from the TNs. A lot of materials are produced, but end-users may struggle to identify which information and materials are specifically dedicated to them.’

‘Languages and translations remain the main barrier of C&D activities. TNs are trying to translate at the maximum but it comes to a lack of resources in terms of budget and time. For sure, on-field events must be translated and local partners should make the effort to disseminate in local language as much as possible’.

Table 14. Communication and Dissemination - TN Output Format

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
C&D	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	Technical content, best practices, and methodologies presented in a visualized way	No. of technical content, best practices, and methodologies	Skilled C&D persons List of material

 Budapest recommendation 18: TN Separate Communication & Dissemination:

Regarding: **TN content, TN Communication & Dissemination**

To maximize their impact, TNs should have a **clear understanding of the difference between communication & dissemination** (the latter only being focused on promoting the uptake of results).

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D2.3:

‘All TNs are communicating and disseminating, but the impact isn’t as successful as expected. Even with elaborated C&D plans, the activities are time-consuming for a low vision of end-user engagement and uptake of results. The plans don’t seem to be read or taken up by all TNs partners as C&D is not the first objective for all partners.’

‘C&D appears as a constraint for TN partners, and the partner responsible must find some motivational strategies to involve people. Efficiency should be more stimulated and can be improved by internal communication and by sharing projects and networks’ solutions, strategies, and tools.’

‘The most common difficulties in C&D are often related to a lack of time from the actors involved, as well as a lack of expertise or the budget dedicated to these activities. That’s the reason why detailed planning and sharing of the actions under a timeline is strongly advised to TNs.’

‘The distinction between C&D is not that simple: even if the strategy differs, it ends most of the time with common practice. Although messages, materials, channels, and tools are separated according to target groups and TN objectives, it is challenging to apply it in practice, mostly because of the identification of end-user and the key messages to address.’

Table 15. Communication and Dissemination - TN Separate Communication & Dissemination

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
C&D	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	Involvement of a professional communicator/disseminator in the TN consortium		Apply competencies in the conceptual phase
	A separate communication plan with target audience well defined adapted materials, tools, and channels		Definition and mapping of the target group
	A separate dissemination plan with target audience well defined adapted materials, tools, and channels		Definition and mapping of the target group
	A separate exploitation plan with target audience well defined adapted materials, tools, and channels		Definition and mapping of the target group
	Execution of plans above		All plans presented above are understood and accepted by consortium early in the TN phase

 Budapest recommendation 19: TN Resources Dissemination:
Regarding: **TN Communication & Dissemination**

A major part of the budget and resource allocation should be spent on actual **dissemination**. Potentially even adding a separate project on this **after the project has ended**. This is to maximize the impact of outputs created during the original TN project timeline to benefit the wider farming community. Resources and (financial) incentives to engage ‘end-users’ are needed and to connect local OGs across Member States in a peer-to-peer fashion.

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.3:

‘Measure the engagement and uptake of end-users in C&D activities is highly complicated, as well as the success of the channels, tools, and materials. There is currently no effective tool to measure impact, and TNs are wondering how to evaluate their practices and how can it be adapted in the future’.

*‘To maximize the impact of communication and dissemination, a solution can be to **connect the TNs to other H2020 projects**, national and local projects or OGs, to launch shared events and common reflections to identify innovative practices’.*

Table 16. Communication and Dissemination - TN Resources Dissemination

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
C&D	Qualitative	Quantitative	
Post project period		Budget allocated to dissemination	Budget
		No of planned dissemination activities including post-project	Count activities
		No. of linkages (joint activities) with OGs, national and local initiatives with involvement of end-user groups	Mapping of OG’s and other local groups Count linkages

5.2.4. Major conclusions and impact indicators related to Multi actor approach collected and shared by TNs

TN multi-actor approach (who is involved and how)

Task 2.4 relates to the multi-actor approaches by TNs during the project lifetime cycle, conceptualization, initiation, execution, and post-execution phase. The number and types of actors (sector, organization, geographical spread, type of data), as well as the ways actors are collaborating and sharing knowledge, best practices, and methodologies are considered.

Below are the recommendations for an ideal TN, distilled from the workshop in Budapest with major conclusions of Task 2.4 (D2.4 Report on multi-actor approach in the short, medium, and long term and TNs) related to the content of knowledge collected and shared by TNs. Based on these selected recommendations and solutions, quantitative and qualitative indicators have been formulated.

Budapest recommendation 3: TN Roadmap

Regarding: **TN multi-actor approach**.

The TN should have a **flexible roadmap towards the outputs** (e.g. solutions to certain problems) the TN wants to develop, trial, and apply. It should **co-create** these outputs **with the best experts** that are required to solve the problems the TN has identified. Once the TN has gathered an overview of knowledge (as described in 2) a TN may identify that external expert knowledge is required. Here **‘end-users’ and enablers (facilitators) should** work together with experts to develop potential outputs and ensure the user-friendliness and feasibility of the outputs that are being developed. For example, a TN may identify that they need **different actors** to create an enabling environment **for the actual implementation or upscaling of output**, such as proper regulation or value chain cooperation. If needed, the **TN should allow actors to adapt their role flexibly in the TN** as the project matures. The TN provides a **2-way knowledge exchange** between all of the involved actors.

Table 17. Multi-Actor Approach - TN Roadmap

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Multi Actor	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	Flexible roadmap towards the outputs		Develop a continuous check that output is reaching the target group and its needs. Survey of the target group

Budapest recommendation 4: TN Culture

Regarding: **TN multi-actor approach**

It is very important to establish and maintain good alignment of all actors towards the shared goal(s) of the TN. This is the responsibility of the coordinator, but a facilitator can help to make sure that all involved actors have a **clear view of the process, the intermediate steps, and their role within the process**. At the beginning of the project, this should be translated in some sort of TN ‘Code of Conduct’ or rules of engagement to spell out expectations, roles, and governance during the trust-building phase. Moreover, additional resources should be available to create a culture of trust within a TN through team-building exercises to enforce the ‘Code of Conduct’.

Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.4:

‘There is no one size fits all. The multi-actor approach depends on the subject, theme and value chain.’

Table 18. Multi-Actor Approach - TN Culture

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Multi Actor	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	Code of Conduct for TN		Consortium agreement on the Code of Conduct. Presented,

			understood, and accepted by the consortium.
	Clear definition of roles of the actors in the consortium		Discussed, understood, and accepted by the consortium.
		Number of team-building exercises	Count team building – also needed along the period of the TN

 Budapest recommendation 5: TN Facilitation:

Regarding: **TN multi-actor approach**

The co-creation process should be **facilitated with sufficient expertise only**. The facilitator does not need to be an expert in the field of enquiry but must have or build a trusting, respectful relationship with the TN. The role of the facilitator is to guide the TN through the co-creation process, keeping all actors motivated and working together towards their common goal(s). The facilitators' role is also to help the TN recognise when and what external support or different actors are required. The facilitator should have strong soft & process skills and be able to adapt to the needs of the TN. For example, a newly formed TN may require more directive facilitation to begin with, compared to an established TN, which is more self-driven. A facilitator, therefore, needs to demonstrate competence in facilitating multi-actor knowledge exchange and the ability to reflect and adjust their approach as the TN evolves. The facilitator should map the needs, drivers, and competencies of each actor and identify roles, which play to their strengths and facilitate the sharing of knowledge and skills between actors.

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.4:

'The MAA is a dynamic project and may change throughout the projects as roles and functions may be redefined.'

'Innovation brokers, advisors and facilitators play a major intermediary role in the uptake of results'.

Table 19. Multi-Actor Approach - TN Facilitation

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Multi Actor	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	Professional facilitator in the TN consortium or activities		Apply for competences in the conceptual phase
	Use of facilitator for external activities such as workshops, regional innovation hubs, cross-exchange visits		Employment of facilitator

		Number of team-building exercises	Count team building – also needed along the period of the TN
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Budapest recommendation 6: TN Structure

Regarding: **TN multi-actor approach**

The TN should have a **multi-layered structure** in the network taking into account the **local, national, cross-regional, and EU levels from start to finish** to create **impact at all levels**. There should be dynamic links at the national/EU-level with regular meetings to facilitate communication between each level and overall coordination. Each participating Member State should be represented by a consortium partner.

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.4:

‘The MAA of TNs should be thought and performed at European, national, regional, and local level to be fully efficient.’

Table 20. Multi-Actor Approach - TN Structure

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Multi Actor	Qualitative	Quantitative	
		Equal distribution in the consortium between partners from different European regions	No. of partners in consortium per European region
	Use of facilitator for external activities such as workshops, regional innovation hubs, cross-exchange visits		Employment of facilitator
	Actors at the local, national, cross-regional and EU level involved in the TN		Engaging Multi Actors in the conceptual phase

Budapest recommendation 9: TN User Interaction

Regarding: **TN content**, **TN content storage**, TN Communication & Dissemination, **TN multi-actor approach**

The digital platform should **use user analytics** to optimize its usability further, including **evaluation and feedback forms** on the solutions and outputs it generates. For example, via user reviews of content, content suggestions (e.g. Amazon function: *‘user that was interested in this was also interested in these alternatives’*) or a ‘bot’ that flags up other information that is relevant for you in an interactive virtual conversation (Q&A). This would facilitate a live, interactive

experience for the user and enable the TN to **improve the outputs and adapt them**, so they stay relevant (see the iterative spiral from the ‘Community of Practice’). *E.g. 4D4F, measured outreach with user analytics in a learning community e.g. FarmDemo hub that was set up by AgriDemo-F2F, PLAID and, Nefertiti uses questions, instead of keywords or categories, to guide the users to the results that are most relevant for them.*

Table 21. Multi-Actor Approach - TN User Interaction

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Multi Actor	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	Output targeted users		User survey on platform
	Output adapted by users		User survey at local meeting or workshops

Budapest recommendation 12: TN Community Of Practice

Regarding: **TN Communication & Dissemination**, **TN multi-actor approach**

The TN should build and grow an **interactive ‘Community of Practice’** that can refine the solutions and enhance the uptake **in an iterative learning spiral by creating regional pilots and by A/B testing in different regions to take into account regional differences**. The TN can build this community from scratch or it can try to involve and leverage existing communities (e.g. farmer networks, cooperatives, NGOs,...). It is the facilitator’s responsibility to recognise that an existing community may have very different needs compared to a newly established community and to adjust the approach accordingly. The TN will assign equal weight to the ideas and input from all members of the network, asking questions of end-users and valuing everyone's input, regardless of perceived status. Again, the facilitator's responsibility is to make sure that everyone can contribute to the direction of travel of the TN (*E.g. SKIN¹⁹ has developed an online platform for the implementation of a Virtual Community of Practice “Keep it short”, in order to support the existing network and expand it with new end-users but also to exchange news, experiences and ensure the sustainability of the SKIN outputs*).

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by *D.2.4: “The involvement of many types of actors does not guarantee as such better involvement of all actors to enhance knowledge exchange and impact. The impact can also be achieved by the involvement of the actors, in particular end-users, in regional or local innovation hubs or networks and the use of facilitators. The facilitator model seems to be successful”. “The MAA networks should be vertically and horizontally integrated”.*

Table 22. Multi-Actor Approach - TN Community of Practice

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Multi Actor	Qualitative	Quantitative	

¹⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/short-supply-chains-knowledge-innovation-network>

	Iterative learning spiral including multi actors		Use the facilitator locally. Facilitators are aware of different needs for multi actors in existing and new groups.
		No. of participants in local groups	Counting at meetings
		No. of participants in digital networks	Digital counting
		Coordination and WP lead by participants from all regions of Europe	Prepare in the conceptual phase

 Budapest recommendation 14: TN Digital Support:

Regarding: **TN content storage**, **TN Communication & Dissemination**, **TN multi-actor approach**

The TN should provide **digital support structures** that allow sharing **problems, expertise, solutions and** that can **bring actors together**. This should be done **engagingly and interactively**, e.g. via a chat forum, WebTV with videos or podcasts to engage young potential farmers, and allow farmers to ask each other for help and facilitate questions and sharing of knowledge between users. Potentially, this could be built or interact with existing social media platforms, like Facebook, Instagram, or Reddit (e.g. Olivipedia).

Table 23. Multi-Actor Approach - TN Digital Support

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Multi Actor	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	Digital structure support interactive behaviour	No. of chat forums, WebTV	Knowledge of web design Counting at website
		No. of users of chat forums, WebTV	Counting at website

 Budapest recommendation 16: Peer-To-Peer Exchange

Regarding: **TN Communication & Dissemination**

The TN should take into account the **innovation adaptation curve** (innovator > early adopter > majority > laggards) and spend the majority of their focus on those ‘end-users’ they can reach that act as **influencers** (80/20-rule). As such, it should have a clear strategy with support tools to leverage this knowledge transfer effect and allow farmers to communicate more with other farmers and exchange ideas via **F2F meetings and cross-visits**. Elements of gamification or organizing an award can also be useful. E.g. *Newbie award for new entrant business models as inspiration for other farmers*.

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.4:

‘The farmers or foresters who participate in TN project activities are mainly innovators and early adopters, there is a need to involve and reach the early majority for a project to be successful.’

‘Farmers are less involved in the conceptual phase than researchers, advisors, farmers associations, and facilitators.’

‘Farmers need to be approached in an informal setting and an environment that creates trust, project activities to involve them should be farmer oriented such as study visits and as side events to their existing initiatives such as fairs’.

‘A wide range of MA participatory activities are being organized within TN projects such as workshops, cross-exchange visits, demonstration events, case studies, and training’.

Table 24. Multi-Actor Approach - Peer-to-Peer Exchange

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Multi Actor	Qualitative	Quantitative	
		No. of participatory activities such as workshops, cross-exchange visits, demos, case studies, and training oriented to and with the participation of users	Count activities
		No of attendances at study days, fairs, and other end-user events	Count attendances
	Participatory activities such as workshops, cross-exchange visits, demos, case studies, and training oriented to and with the participation of users		Mapping interests of actors Use facilitator A clear scope of activities

Budapest recommendation 18: TN Separate Communication & Dissemination:

Regarding: **TN content storage**, **TN Communication & Dissemination**

TNs should have **separate communication and dissemination & exploitation plans**, tailored and targeted to specific audiences, **with separate monitoring systems** during and after the project execution in place to evaluate their outreach, the usefulness of their outputs, the actual uptake of results and to **estimate their direct and indirect impact** whenever possible.

E.g. [Agridemo-F2F](#) did try to analyse impact by doing telephone interviews 6 months after the demos.

The Budapest recommendation is illustrated by D.2.4:

'The main type of actors engaged in TN consortia are (in descending order): technical institutions, universities, public research institutions, farmers groups, enterprises, and associations. Advisors, educational institutions, NGOs and media, farmers, and media are underrepresented.'

'Only half of the TNs are 100% demand-driven, meaning that half of the TNs are not oriented to the end-users' needs, farmers and foresters.'

'There is a need for more involvement from end-users during the project, in particular during the conceptual phase, this may e.g. be done through surveys and advisory boards.'

'The MAA is considered as important to contribute to content creation of the knowledge reservoirs produced by the TNs, but also to content for advisory systems and networking.'

'According to the EIP-AGRI end-users of MA projects are considered to be farmers and foresters, and potentially advisors or innovation brokers as key intermediaries between the research and the practice. TNs also consider farmers associations, policy-makers, researchers, and facilitators as important end-users groups.'

'Depending on the topic of the TN (water management, plant protection...), the relevant authorities (water authorities, plant protection authorities...) should be also involved.'

'A post-project phase is needed to evaluate the outcome and uptake of results by the end-user, further reflection is needed on how to evaluate this and which type of evaluation methodologies and indicators should be used.'

Table 25. Multi-Actor Approach - TN Separate Communication & Dissemination

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Multi Actor	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	Roadmap for co-creation and involvement of actors during the project's life cycle		Roadmap presented, discussed, understood and accepted by all partners early in TN life
	Uptake of results in the post-execution phase		Evaluation in the post executive phase
		No. of different key actors involved	Count actors
		No. of end-users involved in the different phases of the project life cycle	Count users
		No. of evaluations performed in the post-execution phase	Prepare evaluations before TN ends.

The ‘type of data required’ is not straightforward. Depending on the indicator it can be understood as ‘data required’ but in other cases as ‘how to achieve’ the indicators. This explanation also implies that the indicators suggested are also not straightforward. In some cases, they act more as a goal.

All quantitative and qualitative indicators based on task 2.1 – 2.4 and Budapest recommendations for the ideal TN are listed in a summary table (see below).

Table 26. Table of indicators 1

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
	Qualitative	Quantitative	
Purpose	Problem-solving approach		Needs of farmers, foresters and advisors
	A well-defined, clear scope		Goals defined during the conceptualisation phase
Knowledge	State of the art knowledge collected early in the period of a TN and shared with all TN partners		State of the art review of existing knowledge research and grey literature
		No. of disciplines involved in the TN consortium in the conceptualisation phase	Shared competences of all TN-partners
		No. of disciplines involved in the TN activities during the project.	An updated list of topics, activities, and participants during the lifespan of a TN
Knowledge and regions		Equal distribution in the consortium between partners in different European regions	No. of partners in consortium per European region
Output	Output relevant and practically applicable for users		Users’ needs for practical solutions
	Easy understandable language		Knowledge of which languages users understand
	Terminology oriented to practitioners		Knowledge of common terminology among users
		No. of local languages per output	List of outputs and languages
		No. of different outputs	List of outputs

Table 27. Table of indicators 2

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Content storage	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	User-friendly access		User tests
	Search engine tool		Knowledge of users' needs
	Automatic profiling and translation		Knowledge of users' profile and language
		No. of user-friendly functionalities	User tests
	Digital platform with possibilities for user analytics		Definitions of useful analytic techniques. Content rating tools.
	User interactive digital platform		Knowledge of applicable techniques and layout
		No. of interactions on digital platform	Counts of interactions. Traffic analytics
	Involvement of a professional web designer		Competences for web design
	Attractive layout of the TN website		User tests
	Technical content and best practices easy to find on the website		User tests
	Open access according to the FAIR principle		Well defined specifications for the platform
	Interactive platform		Knowledge of applicable techniques and layout
	Evaluation and feedback mechanisms (surveys for rating by users)		
		User analytics numbers	Counting techniques
		Number of linkages of the website with social media	Counting techniques
	An exploitation plan for the open-source knowledge reservoir of the TN.		Exploitation plan defined along with designing the reservoir

	Sustainability of the project's website after the lifespan of the project		More budget and plan than data
		Number of linkages to networks	Counting possibilities on the platform
		Number of linkages to external data repositories	Counting possibilities on the platform
		Number of months that the website with the TN outputs stays available after the ending of the project	Not possible to measure within the lifespan of TN

Table 28. Table of indicators 3

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
C&D	Qualitative	Quantitative	
Materials		No. of scope related material	Clear scope List of material
		No. of problem-solving material	Users' needs List of material
Channels	List of resources trusted by users		Mapping exercise on trusted channels
	Use of well-established networks and meeting		Mapping exercise on trusted networks and meetings
Training modules and webinars	Focused on end-user needs and involving teaching	No. of training	Participant surveys Count modules
		No. of webinars	Count webinars
	Training and education linked to existing education	No. of linkages with local training initiatives and educational programmes for users	Mapping of existing education Count linkages
	Skilled teachers		Engaged teachers along with developing training Participant surveys

	C&D format, tools, and channels according to the type of content and target audience		Mapping users preferred format, tools, and channels
	Subgroups of target audiences (younger versus older, male versus female, etc.)		Knowing the diversity of users
		No. of specific channels used (podcast, radio, local agricultural, field days, studies, demo's, peer to peer) to reach a specific end-user audience	Count channels
	Professional C&D in the TN consortium or activities		Apply for competences in the conceptual phase
	Professional innovation brokers in the TN consortium or in activities		Apply for competences in the conceptual phase
	Technical content, best practices, and methodologies presented in a visualised way	No. of technical content, best practices, and methodologies	Skilled C&D persons List of material
	Involvement of a professional communicator/disseminator in the TN consortium		Apply competencies in the conceptual phase
	A separate communication plan with target audience well defined adapted materials, tools, and channels		Definition and mapping of the target group
	A separate dissemination plan with target audience well defined adapted materials, tools, and channels		Definition and mapping of the target group
	A separate exploitation plan with target audience well defined adapted materials, tools, and channels		Definition and mapping of the target group

	Execution of plans above		All plans presented above are understood and accepted by consortium early in the TN phase
Post project period		The budget allocated to the dissemination	Budget
		No of planned dissemination activities including post-project	Count activities
		No. of linkages (joint activities) with OGs, national and local initiatives with involvement of end-user groups	Mapping of OG's and other local groups Count linkages

Table 29. Table of indicators 4

Topic	Definition of indicator		Type of data required
Multi Actor	Qualitative	Quantitative	
	Flexible roadmap towards the outputs		Develop a continuous check that output is reaching the target group and its needs. Survey of the target group (s).
	Code of Conduct for TN		Consortium agreement on Code of Conduct. Presented, understood, and accepted by the consortium.
	Clear definition of roles of the actors in the consortium		Discussed, understood, and accepted by the consortium.
		Number of team-building exercises	Count team building – also needed along the period of the TN
	Professional facilitator in the TN consortium or activities		Apply for competences in the conceptual phase
	Use of facilitator for external activities such as workshops, regional innovation hubs, cross-exchange visits		Employment of facilitator

		Number of team-building exercises	Count team building – also needed along the period of the TN
		Equal distribution in the consortium between partners from different European regions	No. of partners in consortium per European region
	Use of facilitator for external activities such as workshops, regional innovation hubs, cross-exchange visits		Employment of facilitator
	Actors at the local, national, cross-regional and EU level involved in the TN		Engaging Multi Actors in the conceptual phase
	Output targeted users		User survey on platform
	Output adapted by users		User survey at local meeting or workshops
	Iterative learning spiral including multi actors		Use the facilitator locally. Facilitators are aware of different needs for multi actors in existing and new groups.
		No. of participants in local groups	Counting at meetings
		No. of participants in digital networks	Digital counting
		Coordination and WP lead by participants from all regions of Europe	Prepare in the conceptual phase
	Digital structure support interactive behaviour	No. of chat forums, WebTV	Knowledge of web design Counting at website
		No. of users of chat forums, WebTV	Counting at website
		No. of participatory activities such as workshops, cross-exchange visits, demos, case studies, and training oriented to and with the participation of users	Count activities

		No of attendances at study days, fairs, and other end-user events	Count attendances
	Participatory activities such as workshops, cross-exchange visits, demos, case studies, and training oriented to and with the participation of users		Mapping interests of actors Use facilitator A clear scope of activities
	Roadmap for co-creation and involvement of actors during the project's life cycle		The roadmap presented, discussed, understood and accepted by all partners early in TN life
	Uptake of results in the post-execution phase		Evaluation in the post executive phase
		No. of different key actors involved	Count actors
		No. of end-users involved in the different phases of the project life cycle	Count users
		No. of evaluations performed in the post-execution phase	Prepare evaluations before TN ends.

5.3. Impact measured in nine Thematic Network reports

In the following, nine final TN reports have been examined to extract indicators for output, outcome, and impact, qualitatively, and quantitatively.

Most TNs introduce the report by presenting the objectives. Some TNs present indicators or measures to verify if the objectives are achieved at the same time. Other TNs report the work carried out during the project in a narrative way. All TNs have a paragraph concerning impact. Some TNs have a narrative approach and some also refer to stakeholder statements, while other TNs use certain indicators to verify impact. It has been found that various TNs have slightly different approaches to the use of the terms output, outcome, and impact. The content of the nine reports is complicated to synchronise into tables and to handle uniformly. Therefore, each TN report has its section below, and conclusions on indicators are drawn after reviewing all nine reports.

5.3.1. SMART-AKIS

2nd periodic report, 1st March 2017- 31st August 2018

Main project objective: to set up a self-sustainable Thematic Network on Smart Farming Technology (SFT)

Introduction

Smart-AKIS narratively introduces the objectives of TN. Indicators of success created at the beginning of the project are displayed in a table, 3-6 indicators per objective, altogether 20 indicators. Key performance indicators of innovation workshops are also presented in a table whereas the impact of the project is explained narratively.

Main findings

Indicators of success are measured as target value and achieved values, and in most indicators that were covered, the achieved value was higher than the target value. Key performance indicators (KPIs) of innovative workshops are all quantitative, whereas impact is reported narratively.

Table 30. SMART-AKIS

Indicators		Impact
Qualitative	Quantitative	Impact measured
	Key performance indicators of innovation workshops, number of:	From a narrative report: Qualitative and quantitative indicators:
	- Stakeholders participating	1. Improved flow of information and knowledge: 6 successful innovation case studies
	- Solutions presented - Solutions <i>adopted</i>	2. Increased exchanges on innovative matters: - The platform gives the ability to propose SFT as useful for specific users.
	- Grassroots level needs and ideas captured - Needs for research	3. Successful deployment of the vast reservoir: - Included social dimension to innovation by allowing end-users to have increased ownership of SFT
	- Alternative use of SFT	4. Collection of innovative knowledge: - The industry has been constantly informed - Close communication with EIP-AGRI ServicePoint. - SCAR-AKIS has been briefed
	- Project ideas captured	5. TN delivering accessible and long-term available end-user material:

		<p>The number of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Entries - Practice Abstracts - Videos - Policy briefs - Policy recommendations
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initiations of multi-actor innovation collaborations 	<p>6. Improved skills and education material: Only 7,3% of the presented on the platform SFTs were assessed negatively</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initiations of multi-actor cross-border collaborations and exchanges. 	<p>7. Support for EIP-AGRI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Link with a large number of OGs - Link with EIP-clusters - Link with other TNs and other multi-actor projects - Collection and dissemination of outcomes

Additional information that influences impact:

SMART-AKIS has assessed the Smart Farming Technology available at the platform.

SMART-AKIS has produced specific SFTs with six success stories, which will improve stakeholders’ skills.

SMART -AKIS is hosted on a dedicated platform.

From the interview in D2.1: SMART-AKIS indicated that they have tried to involve industrial partners, who would be willing to fund further activities.

Conclusion

To set up a self-sustainable TN three crucial indicators are selected:

1. Grassroots level needs and ideas captured
2. Social dimension to innovation included by allowing end-users to have increased ownership of the SFT
3. Assessment of SFT

Extra: Funds for further activities

5.3.2. SheepNet

2nd Periodic Technical Report 30th April 2018- 1st October 2019

Project title: Sharing expertise and experience towards sheep productivity through networking.

Introduction

SheepNet introduces the objectives of the TN narratively and explains impacts in a narrative way. Indicators of impact are listed in an updated table.

Main findings

Table 31. SheepNet

Definition of indicator		Impact
Qualitative	Quantitative	Impact measured
Regional examples to the local and national authorities	Impact indicators to be evaluated during the project. The number of:	Based on quantitative impact indicators SheepNet concludes on the following impacts:
SHEEPNET advisory board → interconnection with policymakers at EU level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fact sheets - Ideas captured 	1. Successful deployment of the vast reservoir: SheepNet has created a strong link between researchers and end-users. e.g. 32 national/regional networks, 59 innovative farms
Use existing channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Barriers limiting adaptation - Visits to the platform - Followers on social media 	2. Collection and provision so that the material remains available in the long term: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Translated into 5 languages - 150 PA
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordination with other TNs, MAP, OGS - Institutions and policymakers reached 	3. Greater user acceptance: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identified 68 existing channels - Analysis of end-users' needs - Focus on potential barriers to the implementation of innovative processes.
	To be evaluated at the end of the project: The number of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stakeholders invited to and attending the final seminar - Stakeholders attending national seminars - Innovative sheep farming solutions adopted by practitioners. 	4. The increased flow of practical information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact 80% of EU sheep production. - A tour Oceanian to initiate a long interaction and potential collaboration is organised.

Additional information that influences impact:

SheepNet organised an Oceanian tour to initiate a long interaction and potential collaboration with sheep actors in New Zealand and Australia. The SheepNET Knowledge Reservoir is in its own right hosted by the

project site. Indicator by the end of the project: innovative sheep farming solutions *adopted* by practitioners.

From interviews in task 2.1: Initiatives to be highlighted for the SheepNet KR is the major effort put into translating the content into the partners' different languages.

The impact indicators used by SheepNet is the same kind of indicators that e.g. SMART-AKIS uses as key performance indicators. The impact indicators are more output indicators than impact indicators. It is still worth measuring the indicators but it is clearer to name them output indicators. SheepNet has assessed “innovative sheep farming solutions” as *adopted*, which means that behaviour or habits have been changed for one or more farmers. It is an outcome and a step forward to achieve impact. However, it is not clear how SheepNet has assessed the adoption. This assessment would be a relevant outcome indicator.

Conclusion

To share expertise and experience through networking, three crucial indicators are selected:

1. SHEEPNET advisory board => interconnection with policymakers at EU level
2. Identify existing channels
3. No. of innovative sheep farming solutions adopted by practitioners (specify how to measure this)

5.3.3. Winetwork

Final report April 2015 – September 2017

Project title: Network for the exchange and transfer of innovative knowledge between European Wine-growing regions to increase the productivity and sustainability of the sector.

Introduction

Winetwork has delivered the shortest report of all with not any table. However, Winetwork provides interesting reflections on making a replication of the project and on potential impacts.

Main findings

Table 32. Winetwork

Definition of indicator		Impact
Qualitative	Quantitative	Impact measured
<i>In between indicator and recipe:</i>	The number of:	Regarding the use of the existing platform - Free and easy access to all material - Strong communication - High quality of deliverables - Following impacts are measured:

<p><i>Three key elements:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Networks of trained facilitators with technical knowledge supported by technical and methodological coordinators 2. Advisory board (researchers of the topic) 3. Technical workgroups on specific topics (farmers, technicians) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use existing platform - Free and easy access to all material created - <i>(strong communication and quality of deliverables)</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Actors - Regions - People involved - People to synthesise best Practice - Facilitators - Scientific profiles - Interviews - Meetings (workshops, face-to-face) - Documents (technical datasheets, technical articles, scientific articles, posters, power points, videos, training, and flyers) - Languages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research actors feed and will continue to feed the KR - National representative organizations of winegrowers who used and will use KR deliverables in their communication.
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Additional information that influences impact:

Winetwork concluded that quantitative indicators made it possible to disseminate the results more widely and to challenge national actors outside the consortium.

From interviews (task 2.2): The knowledge access path in the Winetwork KR is interesting. We start on the KR with the choice of language (linked to the languages of the project partners), then we choose the type of content we are looking for, which allows us to access different content.

Conclusion

Winetworks own words are selected as three crucial elements to achieve goals:

1. Networks of trained facilitators with technical knowledge supported by technical and methodological coordinators
2. Advisory board (researchers of the topic)
3. Technical working groups on specific topics (farmers, technicians)

5.3.4. HENNOVATION

2nd Periodic Technical Report Part B 1st March 2016 - 31st August 2017

Project title: Practice lead innovation supported by science and market-driven actors in the laying hen and other livestock sectors.

Introduction

HENNOVATION introduces the objectives and how they are achieved in a table. Besides this, the report is in the text where indicators are extracted.

Main findings

The report provides many good hand-drawn infographics, which have been co-produced in networks during the lifespan of the project.

Table 33. HENNOVATION

Definition of indicator		Impact
Qualitative	Quantitative	Impact measured
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-farm networks - Off-farm networks - Trained facilitators - Facilitator network - Research carried out parallel to practice-led innovation network - Video promoting - Written material co-produced - Exercise to identify research priorities - Online training course - Participating in meetings related to other livestock sectors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. networks - No. facilitators - No. member states - Facilitation guidelines - No. videos - No. visual materials - No. written technical material - No. extension manuals - No. training course - No. Practice abstracts - Technical notes - Presentation during civil dialogue group (CDG) - Presentation on Animal Product sector - Project partners participating in meetings 	

Additional information that influences impact:

Outcome from qualitative indicators – Dairy and pig sectors are planning to use the same methods.

Conclusion

To create practice-led innovation, three crucial indicators are selected:

1. Trained facilitators
2. No. networks
3. No. visual materials

5.3.5. EUFRUIT

2nd Periodic Technical Report Part B 1st March 2016 – 28th February 2019

Main project objective: EU fruit network on reduction of pesticide residues on fruit and in the environment

Introduction

EUFRUIT reports mostly in a narrative way. In the impact section, several outcomes of the project are mentioned.

Main findings

During the project, there was a need to present the project findings clearly and simply to growers to maximize impact and uptake. EUFRUIT has produced outputs like:

- Flyers/leaflets/newsletters
- Seminars/lecture-based workshops
- Field-based workshops/open days/field visits
- Participated in conferences/industry events/exhibitions
- Participated in general public events

Based on output and outcome written in the impact section, EUFRUIT concludes:

EUFRUIT has contributed to an increased innovation capacity and competitiveness across sectors.

The expected impact objectives of the EUFRUIT project remain specifically aligned to the work programme and has delivered in terms of:

- ‘Closing the research and innovation divide: the crucial role of innovation support services and knowledge exchange’;
- ‘Improving the flow of information and knowledge between academia and practitioners in particular on agricultural practices and innovations’;
- ‘Increasing exchanges between European regions on innovative matters’;
- ‘Successfully deploying the vast reservoir of existing scientific and practical knowledge’
- ‘Focusing on the collection of innovative knowledge within the four thematic areas of EUFRUIT, to ensure greater user acceptance and intense dissemination of solutions for more competitive and sustainable agriculture to farmers and other actors in the agricultural innovation chain’;
- ‘Delivering accessible and long-term available end-user material on the thematic areas of EUFRUIT thereby generating a better targeted and shared research agenda for innovation-driven research and multi-actor projects’;
- ‘Improving skills and education material on innovation approaches within the specific thematic areas of EUFRUIT’
- ‘Support to implementation of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP) ‘Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability’.

Specifically, the International Expert Groups of EUFRUIT have conducted three scanning and synthesis rounds, and the partners have continually disseminated the resulting best-practice knowledge across the fruit sector value-chain through the established stakeholder networks. The outputs and outcomes mentioned above are all important to move towards impact and therefore worth learning from.

Conclusion

To run an innovative network, three crucial indicators are derived from the reported output and outcomes:

1. Project findings presented clearly and simply to growers
2. Scanning and synthesis rounds, and disseminating the results continuously
3. Accessible and long-term available end-user material

5.3.6. 4D4F

2nd Periodic Technical Report Part B 1st September 2017 – 28th February 2019

Project title: Data-driven dairy decisions for farmers.

Introduction

Results from seven objectives are reported as eleven different outputs. The rest of the report is narrative.

Main findings

Indicators extracted from the text:

Table 34. 4D4F

Definition of indicator		Impact
Qualitative	Quantitative	Impact measured
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Kind of members: farmers, advisers, technology suppliers - Translated material 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Members of CoP - Best practice guides, infographics, best practice videos - Number of languages - Farm events, workshops 	

Additional information that influences the possibility to foresee impact:

4D4F report their *results* closely related to the objectives. The results fall into at least three different categories:

1. 29 videos posted => number of videos posted, nothing about quality and you cannot tell if anybody has watched them (quantitative output indicator)
2. 12 best practices delivered, updated and translated => number of PA + quality “updated and translated” but do not know if anybody has read them (quantitative and qualitative output indicator)
3. 24 SOPs developed and tested and including integration into four management operating systems => number of SOPs + testing + integrated (quantitative and qualitative output indicator and qualitative outcome indicator – next step would be to verify if the integrated SOP is used by farmers)

In the report from specific WP are not only the number of participants at the meetings measured but also *the kind of meeting* (workshop, events) and further *the topics covered* are explained. So, for meetings both quantitative and qualitative output indicators are used.

Besides, the participant feedback was collected:

Farmers left with increased knowledge of what to do with data from sensors. Farmers now understand how to make the best of software programmes and will implement this on their farms. Farmers see advantages for animal welfare by using sensors. There is an increased uptake of sensor technologies at farms in the future – particularly rumination sensors, and lameness sensors. Farmers acknowledged that sensors can highlight health issues before they become apparent to experienced stock-people. There was positive feedback for farm visits (qualitative output indicator).

4D4F define the impact on their impact report:

“The impact of 4D4F will be in an increased uptake, and better use of, sensors and technology in dairy farming, and the development of innovation.”

In multi-actor networks, 4D4F has demonstrated that the new technology “can go beyond the diagnostic capabilities of experienced stock-people”. The difficulty is to measure the extent to which 4D4F has influenced the increase in uptake of sensors and the better use of data. What we can measure are the website statistics.

By defining the indicators precisely, 4D4F comes close to find out if the thematic network is creating impact.

Conclusion

The 4D4F report shows several good examples of qualitative and quantitative indicators on both outputs and outcomes. The project activities have been well prepared and are closely related to the objectives of the project with clear goals and well-defined indicators.

To make data-driven decisions for farmers, three crucial indicators are selected:

1. Meetings (number, kind of meeting, kind of participants and number, topics covered)
2. Feedback from meetings, farm visits etc.
3. Ongoing measuring of website statistics

5.3.7. AGRIFORVALOR

2nd Periodic Technical Report Part B 1st March 2016 – 31st August 2018

Project title: Bringing added value to the agriculture and forest sectors by closing the research and innovation divide.

Introduction

AGRIFORVALOR has reported, “Activities to achieve the objectives” (related to WPs) and “Measurable indicators of achieved specific objectives” related to six specific objectives in a table.

Main findings

AGRIFORVALOR has defined measurable indicators of achieved specific objectives:

Table 35. AGRIFORVALOR

Definition of indicator		Impact
Qualitative	Quantitative	Impact measured
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Steering committees in place - Priority lists of innovative ideas - Final Innovation toolbox dedicated to farmers and foresters - Mentoring and coaching for business model development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MA workshops - Regional innovation and business case study - Innovation partnership groups on exploitation topics - Innovation partnership groups on innovative ideas - Innovation partnership groups on exploitation topics formed - Training workshop courses - Site visits at good practice cases - Workshop courses - E-learning modules - Business model cases - Business model awards - Operational groups - Good practice cases - E-Guideline for mentors - Press articles - Videos on the best business model - E-magazine with research and innovation results - E-Guideline on how to set-up multi-actor innovation networks and projects - Recommendation for European research agenda - Final dissemination event 	

Most of the indicators are countable like “MA workshops” and “Priority lists of innovative ideas (1 per hub)” and act as quantitative indicators. However, several indicators could also be placed in a category of quantitative indicators like:

- Steering committees in place – E.g. if the steering committee is well defined in a specific way of this project like AGRIFORVALOR did: “Scientific steering committee to support exploitation is nominated and selected per hub MS”
- Priority lists of innovative ideas – E.g. if the lists are evaluated by stakeholders
- Final Innovation toolbox dedicated to farmers and foresters – E.g. if the tools in the toolbox are already tested by farmers and foresters

The following are qualitative indicators on outputs achieved by the end of the project; they could just as well be deliverables:

- E-Guideline on how to set-up multi-actor innovation networks and projects -
- Recommendation for European research agenda, final dissemination event.

In the paragraph of “Impact” “AGRIFORVALOR commits itself to produce high-quality end-user and dissemination materials which are easily accessible and contain easy to understand information.” In the table of expected impact, AGRIFORVALOR mentions under the column “criteria to measure the impact”: 24 good practices (leaflets) and 9 MA workshops. The H2020 definition of impact is: “the wider societal, economic or environmental cumulative *changes over a longer period*”. Leaflets and workshops do not in themselves make changes (impact) and AGRIFORVALOR cannot within the lifetime of the TN measure if their outputs will make changes in the long run. What AGRIFORVALOR reports are that they have done everything possible for a TN to achieve impact in the longer run.

Wordings like “measurable indicators” and “impact” are used in slightly different ways to the H2020 definition that can confuse.

Conclusion

To bring added value by closing the research and innovation divide, three crucial indicators are selected:

1. Scientific steering committee to support exploitation is nominated and selected per hub MS
2. End-user and dissemination materials of high quality (define what is meant by high quality, easily accessible and easy to understand information)
3. List of innovative ideas evaluated and prioritised by stakeholders

5.3.8. FERTINNOWA

2nd Periodic Technical Report Part B 1st July 2017 – 31st December 2018

Project title: Transfer of innovative techniques for sustainable water use in fertigated crops

Introduction

FERTINNOWA has reported “objectives” in a table and explained “description of work” to each objective (divided into first and second reporting period). Within “description of work” many measures, which could be named as outputs or indicators, are mentioned.

Main findings

Related to main objectives FERTINNOWA mentions “transfer” and include:

Table 36. FERTINNOWA

Definition of indicator		Impact
Qualitative	Quantitative	Impact measured
- Communication and dissemination plan	For the first period:	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The organisation of the international workshop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FERTINNOWA website (no. visits and users) - Social networks (Twitter account – YouTube channel – Research Gate – Slideshare) - Internal and external digital newsletters - Videos and other multimedia materials - Articles - Practice abstracts - Conferences <p>In the second period FERTINNOWA has updated numbers from the first period and added:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fact sheets - Press releases - Conference abstracts - Peer-reviewed articles - E-book - EIP-Agri mini-papers with a strong link to the FERTINNOWA outcomes 	
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FERTINNOWA has measured the new numbers of the same indicators twice during the lifetime of the project. When numbers like visits on the website are increasing when they know that the website will survive after the end of the project. FERTINNOWA has indications that the outcome of the project will be used and cause impact.

Conclusion

To ensure the transfer of innovative techniques, three crucial indicators are selected:

1. Detailed communication plan
2. Detailed dissemination plan
3. Visits on the website (visits followed during the project)

5.3.9. EURODAIRY

Progress Report 1st August 2017 – 31st January 2019

Project title: A Europe-wide thematic network in support of a sustainable future for EU dairy farmers.

Introduction

EURODAIRY's report on impact is narratively and initiates the topic by acknowledging that "Three years is a relatively short period within which to measure impact. Given the breadth of the subject matter and the extensive reach of project partners, it is quite feasible that there have been specific impacts, which we have not been able to capture".

Main findings

The outcomes are explained narratively by interesting examples:

Exchange of knowledge:

Exchange visits resulted in two farmers changing habits concerning respectively dry period for cows and better cubicle design.

Translation of a leaflet resulted in a veterinarian from one country presented "the Dutch way of reducing antibiotic use".

During a *webinar*, a farmer proposed a new idea, which ended up as a new research project.

Exchange of tools:

An operational group was created specifically to adapt to a specific tool.

EuroDairy outputs are used as teaching material for the Faculty of Agriculture and Biology of the University of Warsaw. Other tools are presented, discussed, or adopted in other countries.

Engagement with the EIP:

An OG used the potential to connect to a thematic network to strengthen its bid, which ultimately proved successful. The value of this connection to a thematic network was subsequently seen via the organisation by EuroDairy of cross border workshops on the subject.

Dissemination techniques:

A good example of successful knowledge transfer and co-operation between science and farmers followed a webinar on extended lactation by a Danish farmer. EuroDairy partners in Finland had good discussions with farmers after the webinar, one of whom began to test extended lactation within the herd at home.

EURODAIRY hopes that some of the connections made by bringing a range of people (farmers, researchers, advisors, policymakers, operational group co-ordinators) together in workshops, exchange visits, and through digital media, will continue to evolve.

EURODAIRY has many precise examples of outcomes of the TN.

Conclusion

To support the sustainable future of farmers, three crucial indicators are selected:

1. Exchange visits (time, amount, whom, how long, to where, etc.)
2. Translation (topic, languages, dissemination route, presentations, etc.)

3. Webinars (topic, schedule, how to announce, target group, etc.)

5.3.10. Summary of Impact measured in nine Thematic Network final reports

Interesting indicators from nine TN reports are divided into four groups: **TN content**, **TN content storage**, **TN Communication & Dissemination**, **TN multi-actor approach**.

TN content

1. End-user and dissemination materials of high quality (define what is meant by high quality, easily accessible and easy to understand information)
2. Assessment of SFT
3. No. of innovative sheep farming solutions adopted by practitioners (specify how to measure this)
4. (Some of the indicators situated in TN Communication & Dissemination could also fit into TN content)

TN content storage

1. Accessible and long-term available end-user material
2. Visits on the website (visits followed during the project)
3. Ongoing measurements of website statistics

TN Communication & Dissemination (and Exploitation)

1. Detailed communication plan
2. Detailed dissemination plan
3. Identify existing channels
4. No. of visual materials
5. Project findings presented clearly and simply to growers
6. Scanning and synthesis rounds, and disseminating the results continuously
7. Translation (topic, languages, dissemination route, presentations, etc.)
8. Webinars (topic, schedule, how to announce, target group, etc.)

TN multi-actor approach.

1. Trained facilitators
2. The network of trained facilitators with technical knowledge supported by technical and methodological coordinators
3. Meetings (number, type of meeting, type of participants and number, topics covered)
4. Feedback from meetings, farm visits, etc.
5. Advisory board (researchers of the topic)
6. SHEEPNET advisory board => interconnection with policymakers at EU level
7. No. networks
8. Technical working groups on specific topics (farmers, technicians)
9. Scientific steering committee to support exploitation is nominated and selected per hub MS
10. Grassroots level needs and ideas captured

11. Social dimension to innovation included by allowing end-users to have increased ownership of the SFT
12. List of innovative ideas evaluated and prioritised by stakeholders
13. Exchange visits (time, amount, whom, how long, to where, etc.)

5.4. Indicators for impact extracted from EURAKNOS mind map

A mind map was developed jointly by EURAKNOS partners to ensure the identification of the key issues related to indicators.

Extracts from the mind map regarding Quantitative indicators are presented below:

TN content:

1. Number of key disciplines involved during the project's life cycle in the consortium and/or TN participatory activities
2. Easily understandable language with a terminology oriented to practitioners
3. Number of materials produced with practice-oriented content
4. Availability of content in a range of languages

TN content storage:

1. Number of user-friendly functionalities
2. User analytics
3. Number of linkages with social media
4. Budget for the website after the lifespan of the project
5. Number of months that the website is still available after the lifespan of the project
6. Number of linkages to external data repositories
7. Compatibility with FAIR data principles
8. Open access
9. End-users use of TN outputs per period like the classical citation.

TN Communication & Dissemination (and Exploitation):

1. Number of training modules
2. Number of local languages in which TN outputs are produced
3. Number of events organised, the number of newsletters produced, number of target 5.4 audience reached, number of hits on the website, etc.
4. An interactive publication list on the web, which counts the number of downloads for each material
5. Number of webinars
6. Number of linkages with local training and educational programmes for farmers, foresters and advisors
7. Number of specific channels used to reach a well-defined audience such as radio, TV, local agricultural press, podcasts, field days, study days, demos, etc.
8. Number of visualised materials e.g. infographics, videos, imagery

9. Number of scientific publications
10. Number of popular articles

TN multi-actor approach:

1. Number of key actors involved
2. Equal distribution between actors from different European regions
3. Equal representation of different fields of expertise
4. Equal representation of different sectors

The entire mind map and the word version of the mind map are located in Annex I.

6. Summary and Conclusion

6.1. Summary

Measuring impact is challenging. What we can do is to evaluate the probability of impact. Well-defined indicators, qualitative as well as quantitative, can measure if an objective has been met, a resource mobilised or an effect obtained.

Indicators presented in the previous chapters are based on:

- Data collected through a desktop study, oral and written interviews of partners and surveys from each of the 28 TNs
- A 3-day workshop where the analysis of the 28 TNs was presented to 32 KIPs
- Reports of nine TNs
- A brainstorm via a mind map conducted by partners in the EURAKNOS project.

Based on the above results the table below represents a condensed and combined overview of all the major indicators that have been collected using the four different sources and methodologies. In total we have identified 29 qualitative and 35 quantitative indicators related to 5 different aspects, the TN purpose, Content storage, Communication and Dissemination (and Exploitation), and the MAA. For the overview it was deliberately chosen to categorize the indicators that are more related to exploitation (instead of dissemination) separately as exploitation is more linked to impact in terms of taking up the TN results in the field. For the purpose of the overview the indicators were listed in a logical order according to the different steps in a life cycle of a project: purpose (user-oriented and flexibility)-MAA (creating ownership and collecting knowledge)- content storage (accessibility and utility, monitoring and evaluation, interactivity, and connectivity) – communication, dissemination (user-oriented and improved information flow)- and exploitation (sustainability, guidelines and tools, improved skills, education and training materials, multiplication, and monitoring and evaluation).

The indicators represent a vast amount of knowledge base on the TN experiences. They could be formulated in response to the question “How would we know whether or not what has been planned is happening or has happened? How do we verify success?”

It should be stressed that this list is not exhaustive, and that the indicators can be used as indicative to make a TN more efficient and hence have more impact in agricultural and/or forestry innovation. Besides, as each TN is different, the most important decision is to choose the right indicators and to apply them appropriately within the respective project context.

Good indicators need to be relevant to the project and its environment, relevant to the national/international standards, feasible to collect, easy to interpret, they should allow tracking a change over time. Good indicators should as much as possible:

- Specify quantity, quality, time
- Be realistic,
- Involve the right people
- Allow reviewing targets regularly,
- Provide incentives to report honestly

Moreover, a good indicator should be SMART:

- **S**pecific to the objective it is supposed to measure,
- **M**easurable (either quantitatively or qualitatively),
- **A**vailable at an acceptable cost,
- **R**elevant to the information needs of managers,
- **T**ime-bound – so it is known when to expect the objective/target to be achieved.

The appropriate use of indicators is to be clear about which objective the indicator belongs to and to set a reasonable time for measuring. It could be a midterm evaluation or even more often to provide possibilities of some adjustments.

Table 37. Overview of indicators related to purpose, the MAA, content storage, communication, dissemination, and exploitation based on TN experiences

Topic	Definition of indicator		Knowledge required	Measures
Purpose	Qualitative	Quantitative		
User oriented	1.Problem-solving approach	1.No of practical solutions shared and presented	Needs of farmers, foresters and advisors	-Surveys and consultations during the conceptualisation phase
	2.A well-defined, clear scope		Objectives defined during the conceptualisation phase	-Brainstorming with a core group of the consortium during the conceptualisation phase
Flexibility	3.Flexible roadmap towards outputs	3. No of checkpoints for evaluation and adaptation	Checkpoints for outputs; is output is reaching the target group and its needs. Survey of the target group (s).	-Development of roadmap in initiation phase of the project in co-creation with consortium partners/key actors -Dynamic project process
MAA	Qualitative	Quantitative		
Creating ownership	4.Code of Conduct for TN	2.No of actors with roles and responsibilities clearly defined based on complementary expertise and profiles	Responsibilities and roles of each actor	-Define code of conduct in the conceptualisation phase
	6.Team building	3.No of team building exercises	-Competences and social skills for team building	-Engagement of a facilitator in consortium and/or project activities
Co-collecting knowledge	7.State of the art knowledge collected early		-Existing knowledge in the	-Review of existing knowledge, tacit knowledge and grey literature

	in the period of a TN and shared with all TN partners		theme/field/sector of the TN	
	8.Multidisciplinary consortium	4.No. of disciplines involved in the TN consortium in the conceptualisation phase and during the project	An updated list of topics, activities, and expertise needed to fulfil the objectives of the project	-Share competences and engage different disciplines in the consortium
	9.Transregional engagement, Involvement of partners from different European regions in the consortium and activities	6.Equal distribution between the different regions in the consortium 7.Equal distribution in the project's activities	-Regional origin of consortium partners -Mapping of key actors in the different European regions	-Partners from Northern, Southern, Western and Eastern regions defined and engaged in the consortium and project activities
	10. Actors at the local, regional, national and EU levels involved in the TN	8.No of local, regional, national and EU levels involved	-Mapping of actors at local, national and EU level	-Defining and engaging multi-actors at several levels in the consortium and/or advisory board and /or activities such as EU, national events regional workshops and local hubs
	11. Engagement of end-user	9.Number of end users (organisations) involved in the consortium 10.Number of joint activities with OGs and end-users	-Mapping of OGs and end-user groups	-Organisation of participatory activities such as workshops, cross-exchange visits, demos, case studies, and training oriented to and with the participation of users
	12. Involvement of (a) facilitator (s) or innovation broker(s) in the consortium or project activities	11.No of activities with facilitator	-Facilitator skills	-Apply for competences in the conceptualisation phase

				-Engagement of a facilitator in the consortium/and or project activities such as regional workshops
Content Storage	Qualitative	Quantitative		
Accessibility and Utility	13.User friendly website with user friendly search engine	12.No of user friendly functionalities 13.No of users 14.No of hits 15.No of visits	-Knowledge of users' need in particular farmers, foresters and advisors -Competences for web design -Traffic analytics	-User tests -Clutter free design and friendly navigation and visibility search engine -Engaged technical content in open access (FAIR) -Involvement of a professional web designer/professional communication team as part of the consortium
	14.Content available in users' local language	16.No of languages	-Knowledge of users' profile and language	-Automatic profiling and translations
Monitoring and evaluation	15.Digital platform with possibilities for user analytics	17.No of user analytics functionalities	-Definitions and knowledge of useful analytic techniques, and content rating tools	-Google analytics -Analysing users to provide invaluable insights
Interactivity	16.User interactive digital platform	18.No of interactive functionalities (chat forums, interactive webinars etc.) 19.No of interactions of digital platforms	-Knowledge of applicable techniques and layout -Traffic analytics	-Peer to peer functionalities

Connectivity	17.Interoperability	20.No of linkages other data repositories	-Interoperable standards -	-Implementing interoperable IT language and functionalities at the web page design phase
Communication & Dissemination	Qualitative	Quantitative		
User oriented	18.Clear scope, technical content with a problem solving approach	21.No. of practice oriented related dissemination materials material	-Knowledge on farmers' and foresters' needs	-Orienting content to end-users' needs
	19.Easy understandable content easy to understand	22.No of easy understandable dissemination materials 23.No of translations in local languages	-Terminology used by farmers and advisors -Local languages	-Utilisation of farmer's language -Translation in local languages
Improved information flow	20.Dissemination through trusted channels	24.No of user traditional channels used	-Mapping exercise on trusted channels in the different European countries/regions involved	-Use of information sources trusted by farmers, foresters and advisors such as agricultural press, well established networks, radio, TV channel, agricultural fairs, study days peer to peer etc.
	21.Professional communication & dissemination		-Skills communicator	-Apply for competences in conceptualisation phase -Engagement of professional C&D in consortium

	22.Subgroups of target audiences (younger versus older, male versus female, etc.)	25.No of subgroups and specific channels used (podcast, radio, local agricultural, field days, studies, demo's, peer to peer) to reach a specific end-user audience	-Knowing the diversity of users and their preferred channels	-Mapping users, preferred format, tools, and channels -Targeted communication and dissemination plan taking into account the subgroups and diversity of users
Exploitation	Qualitative	Quantitative		
Sustainability	23.Post project website	26. No of moths that website is online and functional after the project had ended	-Partner willing to continue to host -Budget needed	-Exploitation plan developed and implemented in the initialisation phase of the project including sustainability (linkages and sustainability after the ending of the project) -Planning of budget including post project phase -Identification of a partner or institution to continue hosting of the website -Allocation of budget
Guidelines & Tools	25. Guide, Handbook, Policy brief, Toolbox	No of guides, Handbooks, Policy briefs produced No of users of above mentioned materials (number of downloads, distributed materials)	-Technical guidelines, recommendations and tool -Needs of target group -Dissemination channels	- Identification of target group and needs - Identification of dissemination channel adapted to target group -Google Analytics -Survey and consultations with user groups
Improved skills, education, and	24.Training modules and webinars	27.No. of training modules developed and implemented	-Knowledge on training needs for	-Development of presentations for trainings, course modules and webinars

training materials		(e.g. through website, local workshops)	advisors, farmers, foresters	-Feedback of end-users
	25.Linkage to existing educational institutions and training initiatives	28.No. of linkages with local training initiatives and educational programmes for farmers foresters, and advisors	-Mapping of existing educational institutions, OGs and existing networks	-Connections to existing, educational institutions, OGs an existing networks - Engagement of trainers and educators - Evaluation of training through servers
	26.Skilled trainers and educators	29.No of training materials professionally developed	-Competences training & education	-Apply for competences in the conceptualisation phase
Multiplication	27.Linkage to existing networks , end-user groups, and the EIP-AGRI	30. No of linkages to existing networks, end-user groups, and the EIP-AGRI	- Mapping of existing networks and end user groups	- Dissemination to existing networks through newsletters, websites
	28.Linkage to social media such as Facebook, LinkedIn, You Tube and Twitter	31.No of linkages to social media 32.No of social media linked	-Mapping of social media and linked audience	- Creating social media accounts - Linking social media to project website
Monitoring and evaluation	29.Uptake of results in the field	33. No of farmers using an TN output 34. No of outputs taken up by farmers 35. No of new innovation partnerships and/or new business model	-Mapping of end user community - Mapping of innovation partnerships formed and new business model cases	- Surveys and consultations with end-users (face to face, mailing, telephone calls etc.) in post project phase

6.2. Conclusion

The long term impact is ‘the wider societal, financial or environmental cumulative change over a longer period’. This impact can neither be reached nor measured within the timespan of a TN. The impact is of highest interest to a TN but cannot be influenced by a TN and is indeed out of the control of a TN. What a TN can do is to make outputs (products) and support outcomes (short to medium term changes in a situation). The most important thing for a TN is to have a clear goal. From the goal outputs and outcomes can be defined. The more precise the better, and from here indicators, qualitative as well as quantitative, can be formulated.

Therefore the framework developed in the context of Task 2.6 and this deliverable can be used for TNs as criteria to measure effectiveness in terms of content, content storage, MAA, communication and dissemination, and exploitation in terms of reaching and engaging the end-user in an efficient way to be able to achieve better impact. The real impact or uptake of the TN results (outcomes) can only be measured in a post-monitoring phase e.g. to surveys, phone calls, face to face meetings, etc. with the end-users.

One of the major aims of EURAKNOS is to ‘stimulate the exchange of existing TN practices and methodologies’. In this report, indicators have been extracted from interviews of coordinators of 28 ongoing and finalised TNs, from evaluation of the results by KIP’s, from reports from nine finalised TNs and a mind map made in collaboration with EURAKNOS partners. In summary, the indicators were presented in categories: (i) content, (ii) storage of content, (iii) MAA, (iv) communication and dissemination, and (v) exploitation. They constitute a base from where future TNs can be inspired to formulate indicators that fit the specific network as criteria to achieve better impact in the sense of enhancing the uptake of results or outputs by the end-user, farmer, forester, and advisor.

7. Next steps

The conclusions from D2.6 feed into WP3 and further work in EURAKNOS. The summary of the current TN methodologies and best practices and the impact framework will be used as a basis for WP3 to select the best practices and methodologies for TNs for creating content, designing the knowledge reservoirs, communication and dissemination, and multi-actor approaches. They will form the basis to develop technical guidelines for TNs to be more effective in reaching the farmers, foresters, and advisors, and speed up the uptake of the outputs.

8. Annex

8.1. Annex I – Mind map on indicators

Mind map on indicators developed in collaboration with partners in EURAKNOS

Measuring TN impact

Figure 1. Visual illustration of the Mind map exercise on indicators

Impact indicators

A Qualitative Indicators

1. *Qualitative indicator for best practices for the multi-actor approach?*

1.1.1 Use of facilitator?

- Some have got new skills

1.1.2 Many of the indicators related to TN are about network performance and increase of the capacity of a network to generate innovation

- Involvement of end-user, farmer, forester, or advisor, in the conceptualisation phase

2. *Categorization*

2.1 *TN Purpose/output*

2.1.1 TN oriented to a problem-solving approach based on the needs and problems of the farmer, forester, and advisor

- TN with a clear and narrow focus
- Overview of existing practical knowledge in the scope of the TN including tacit knowledge produced by farmers and foresters

2.2 *TN Content/outcome*

2.3 *TN open-source Design, Storage/outcome*

2.3.1 User-friendly access

2.3.2 Search engine tool

2.3.3 Automatic profiling and translation

2.3.4 Attractive layout of the website

2.3.5 Open access according to the FAIR principle

2.3.6 Involvement of a professional web designer

2.3.7 Interactive platform

2.3.8 Evaluation and feedback mechanism

2.4 *TN Communication and Dissemination/outcome*

2.4.1 Use of a decision support tool to define the right

2.4.2 communication/dissemination format, tool and channel according to the type of content target audience

2.4.3 Involvement of teachers at vocational schools

2.4.4 Development of educational material

2.4.5 Involvement of trainers for advisors

2.4.6 Engagement of a professional communicator/disseminator

2.4.7 Use of key intermediaries, advisors and innovation brokers

2.4.8 Differentiation in target audience subgroups e.g. older versus younger farmers

2.4.9 Visualisation of practice-oriented knowledge, innovative solutions, best *practices and methodologies*

3. *Indicators related to upscaling*

3.1 Level of satisfaction of members with regard to relevance and affordability of solutions developed.

3.2 Number of network members applying the innovation as common practice.

3.3 Network members' pride in what they achieved. (Do they want to share the idea with others)

4. Indicators related to networking

- 4.1 Link to OGS
- 4.2 Other TNs
- 4.3 Other MA H2020
- 4.4 NRNs
- 4.5 Living Labs

Think about social media shares: a share may be a qualitative indicator as it somehow reflects the user's personality. You just don't share anything but things that you are in line with. Hence, you will need a platform with a sharing system e.g. Facebook, retweets, backtracks in blogging, Instagram links, etc.?

B Quantitative indicators

5. Communication and dissemination:

- 5.1 Number of training modules
- 5.2 Number of local languages in which TN outputs are produced
- 5.3 Number of events organised, the number of newsletters produced, number of target audience reached, number of hits on the website, etc.
 - 5.4.1 Then just put an interactive publication list on the web, which counts the number of downloads for each material
- 5.5 Number of webinars
- 5.4 Number of linkages with local training and educational programmes for farmers, foresters and advisors
- 5.5 Number of specific channels used to reach a well-defined audience such as radio, TV, local agricultural press, podcasts, field days, study days, demos, etc
- 5.6 Number of visualised materials e.g. infographics, videos, imagery
- 5.7 Number of scientific publications
- 5.8 Number of popular articles
- 5.9 *Are these really impact indicators? Or are they still output or potential outcome indicators? An outcome I would say.*
 - 5.9.1 ain question again, is a number/a count = impact? Thus create an impact scale to evaluate the score. Benchmark it with numbers from EURAKNOS, however, it is just comparing numbers.
 - 5.9.2 It is like trolls in forums that go for post counts, but without quality

6. Content

- 6.1 Number key disciplines involved during the project's life cycle in the consortium and/or TN participatory activities
- 6.2 Easy understandable language with a terminology oriented to practitioners
- 6.3 Number of materials produced with practice-oriented content
- 6.4 Availability of content in a range of languages

7. MAA

- 7.1 Number of key actors involved
- 7.2 Equal distribution between actors from different European regions
- 7.3 Equal representation of different fields of expertise

7.4 Equal representation of different sectors

8. Design

8.1 Number of user-friendly functionalities

8.2 User analytics

8.3 Number of linkages with social media

8.4 Budget for the website after the lifespan of the project

8.5 Number of months that the website is still available after the lifespan of the project

8.6 Number of linkages to external data repositories

8.7 Compatibility with FAIR data principles

8.8 Open access

8.9 TN impact factor: end-users use of TN outputs per period like the classical citation. But how to "count" the use. If access to documents:

8.9.1 Equals use by end-user then every counting statistic may be good: downloads, likes, etc.

8.9.2 Listings in web search, let other people rank TNs/EURAKNOS outputs

Can find "new" indicators for better impact pertaining to each investigated aspect: content, design, communication and dissemination, and MA approach

C Impact indicators used by TNs

9. Was there an interview with TN coordinators with the question of how successful do you think your TN is and why?

D Indicators to monitor Horizon 2020 cross-cutting issues

10 SMEs participation

10.1 Percentage of EU Financial contribution going to SMEs

10.2 Percentage of EU financial contribution committed through the SME instrument

11 Social science and humanities

11.1 Percentage of SSH partners on selected Projects in all H2020 priorities and percentage of EU financial contribution allocated to them

12 International cooperation

12.1 Percentage of third-country participants in H2020

E What do we mean with impact? Are we talking about indicators possible to measure within the lifespan of the project?

13. With impact, we mean uptake of results (exploitation) so all indicators that can contribute to this such as an efficient MA approach, best dissemination practices, the content of videos, etc.

14. Not only technical but also social, environmental, etc at the long term

15. But for TN impact, it is like: the thematic of the network --> output --> end-user --> scale of usability (if it went viral then you are good with a very high impact). Was there any aim of the TN, was it achieved? Second step: evaluation of impact by output-material.

15.1 Maybe it can also be possible to push impact in terms of advertisement. Pick an end-user that suits your profile, combine it with output and flush it into media, maybe this goes too far

